
Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

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Introduction

This paper is concerned with the theory of energy potentials that are minimal in open thermodynamic systems whose boundary mass transfer is constrained by the imposition of fixed, possibly externally imposed, chemical potentials. This paper also strives to present a rigorous computational thermodynamic framework for minimization of these potentials with the aim of practical computation of phase equilibria.

The theory presented here augments that of Korzhinskii [Korzhinskii, 1959] who first generalized the concept of the Gibbs phase rule to open systems. The phase rule itself is rooted in the fundamental differential equation [Gibbs, 1876], [Gibbs, 1878] for the chemical evolution of a thermodynamic system,

$$-SdT + VdP - \sum_i^c n_i d\mu_i = 0 \quad (1)$$

which demonstrates that constancy of the intensive thermodynamic variables, namely temperature (T), pressure (P), and component chemical potentials (μ_i) characterize a stationary or equilibrium state¹. Equation (1) may be obtained by Legendre transformations [Callen, 1985] of the combined first and second laws of thermodynamics cast into a form where only expansion work is considered and the disequilibrium contribution to the generation of irreversible heat (i.e., the chemical affinity) is expressed solely by chemical reactions:

$$dE = TdS - PdV + \sum_i^c \mu_i dn_i \quad (2)$$

Equation (1) represents a complete Legendre transformation of equation (2) such that every extensive (mass dependent) differential element is transformed to its intensive equivalent. In essence, the Korzhinskii method that we will follow in this paper constitutes partial Legendre transformations of Equation (2) where some of the extensive compositional variables (i.e., the n_i terms) are replaced by equivalent differentials in chemical potential. The transformed differential equation is then utilized to calculate an equilibrium state by imposing values of chemical potentials on the system. These values are fixed by externally imposed constraints or by specification of the presence of phases in the system that directly bound linear combinations of the chemical potentials. By design, these partial Legendre transformations generate differential equations that *do not* represent a minimum in the Gibbs free energy of the system, or for that matter any of the standard thermodynamic potentials (e.g., internal energy, enthalpy or Helmholtz free energy) *unless the system already satisfies the imposed chemical potential constraints*. Minimization of the system potential that is consistent with a partial Legendre transformation of the compositional terms in Equation (2) requires exchange of mass across the system boundary. These thermodynamic potentials characterize equilibrium in *open* thermodynamic systems that are subject to *generalized constraints on chemical potentials*.

Before proceeding to the theoretical development of these open system potentials, it is important to consider one additional consequence of opening the system boundary to selective mass exchange. In a closed system Duhem's theorem [Duhem, 1899] states that equilibrium can be fully specified using two free thermodynamic variables, e.g., (T, P), (T, V), etc., regardless of the specific identity of phases in the system. This is not the case in an open system subject to generalized chemical potential constraints. Under these circumstances the number of variables that must be specified is two plus the number of imposed constraints. This result may seem surprising, but it follows immediately from Equation (1), which demonstrates that all chemical potentials as well as T and P must not vary in the equilibrium state. If that set of chemical potentials is not implicitly constrained by fixing temperature, pressure and component masses, as in the closed system case, then the fugitive component must have its chemical potential fixed by a constraint imposed at the boundaries of the system.

In the first part of this paper we develop the theory behind generalized thermodynamic potentials and in the remainder of the paper we illustrate case studies and provide petrologic applications.

¹ S denotes the entropy, V the volume, n_i the mole numbers of components, and E the internal energy of the system.

Part I

Theory

GENERALIZED THERMODYNAMIC POTENTIALS

The differential form of the Gibbs free energy (G) of a system may be written [Prigogine and Defay, 1954]:

$$dG = -SdT + VdP + \sum_i^c \mu_i dn_i \quad (1.1)$$

where T , P , and n_i are independent variables denoting the temperature, pressure and number of moles of the i^{th} thermodynamic component in a system of c -components. The entropy of the system is given by S ($= -\frac{\partial G}{\partial T}$), the volume by V ($= \frac{\partial G}{\partial P}$) and the chemical potential of the i^{th} component by μ_i ($= -\frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i}$). The integral form of Equation (1.1) is:

$$G = \sum_i^c \mu_i n_i \quad (1.2)$$

The equilibrium state of a system is characterized by a minimum in the Gibbs free energy at specified temperature, pressure and bulk composition. Under these conditions the system evolves from a disequilibrium to an equilibrium state under the restriction that the system boundary is closed to mass transfer (constant n_i), but is open to heat exchange with its surroundings and to any volume change of the system associated with phase formation. Khorzhinskii [Korzhinskiĭ, 1959] generalized the concept of thermodynamic equilibrium to “open” systems subject to mass exchange with their surroundings for the specific case that the constancy of component mole number may be exchanged with constancy of the equivalent chemical potential, e.g. equilibrium in a system open to exchange of a fugitive component like H₂O may be uniquely determined if the chemical potential of H₂O is somehow externally imposed upon the system. The thermodynamic potential that is minimal under these “open” system conditions is the “Korzhinskii potential” [Ghiorso and Kelemen, 1987], which may be defined by a suitable Legendre transformation of Equation (1.2), e.g., for the example involving H₂O:

$$L = G - \frac{\partial G}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = G - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \quad (1.3)$$

While the usual application of the Khorzhinskii potential is to the characterization of equilibrium in systems constrained by externally fixed chemical potentials, the theory equally applies to the case where a chemical potential, or some linear combination of chemical potentials, is constrained by the demand that a particular phase is present in the system. For example, if the system is forced to be in equilibrium with a pure H₂O fluid phase at some temperature and pressure, then Equation (1.3) also defines the thermodynamic state function that is minimal at equilibrium for these conditions. Note, that the amount of fluid is not known a priori before minimizing L subject to fixed T , P , $n_{i \neq \text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and $\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$; $n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is a derived quantity.

In general, for a phase of fixed stoichiometry¹, indexed as ϕ_j , whose composition can be expressed using the system components vis-a-vis a reaction of the form:

¹ A solution phase consisting of two or more stoichiometric end member components may be treated by writing a statement of Equation (1.4) for each end member; the amount of each end member, i.e. Equation (1.6), thereafter determines the composition of the solution phase. See further discussion later in the text.

the chemical potential of the phase is:

$$\mu_{\phi_j} = \sum_k^c c_{\phi_j k} \mu_k \quad (1.5)$$

The Khorzhinskii potential that guarantees the presence of phase ϕ_j in the assemblage is:

$$L = G - \left(\sum_k^c c_{\phi_j k} n_k \right) \left(\sum_k^c c_{\phi_j k} \mu_k \right) \quad (1.6)$$

For a collection of f -phases, which are assumed to be present in the system, Equation (1.6) is generalized to:

$$L = G - \sum_j^f \left(\sum_k^c c_{\phi_j k} n_k \right) \left(\sum_k^c c_{\phi_j k} \mu_k \right) \quad (1.7)$$

Equation (1.7) is the generalized Khorzhinskii potential for a thermodynamic system containing a specified collection of f -phases.

If the system component mole numbers are collected into a vector, \mathbf{n}_c , and the coefficients $c_{\phi_j k}$ are made the components of a vector \mathbf{R}_{ϕ_j} , then Equation (1.7) may be more compactly written as:

$$L = G - \sum_j^f \mathbf{R}_{\phi_j}^T \mathbf{n}_c \mathbf{R}_{\phi_j} \mu \quad (1.8)$$

1.1 Constraints on the minimum

In order to determine the equilibrium phase assemblage governed by the potential of Equation (1.7), temperature, pressure and the mass of all system components that are not allowed to vary by phase present constraints must be specified. In addition, constraints on chemical potentials, i.e., Equation (1.5), must be imposed in order to guarantee that the stipulated phase assemblage is present at equilibrium. Without the phase present constraints, the specification of a constraint matrix that guarantees constancy of system bulk composition is straightforward, and results in a linear system of equality constraints on the mole numbers of phases in the equilibrium assemblage [Ghiorso, 1985]. For this phase-present scenario, these constraints become more involved.

Consider a system of p -phases at some specified temperature and pressure, with f of those p phases specified or forced to be present in the system. The number of “extra” or non-specified phases is $e \equiv p - f \geq 0$. For the moment, we assume that the identity of the e phases in the system is known¹. At fixed temperature and pressure, the Gibbs phase rule guarantees that $c \geq p = f + e$.

There always exists a linear mapping between the mole numbers of phases present in the system and the mole of the k^{th} system component:

$$n_k = \sum_j^p n_{\phi_j} c_{k\phi_j}^* \quad (1.9)$$

This mapping can be extended to all components and succinctly written in matrix form:

$$\mathbf{n}_c = \begin{bmatrix} n_1 \\ \vdots \\ n_k \\ \vdots \\ n_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{1\phi_1}^* & \cdots & c_{1\phi_j}^* & \cdots & c_{1\phi_p}^* \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{k\phi_1}^* & \cdots & c_{k\phi_j}^* & \cdots & c_{k\phi_p}^* \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ c_{c\phi_1}^* & \cdots & c_{c\phi_j}^* & \cdots & c_{c\phi_p}^* \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\phi_1} \\ \vdots \\ n_{\phi_k} \\ \vdots \\ n_{\phi_p} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{n}_\phi \quad (1.10)$$

¹ [Ghiorso, 2013] describes algorithms for estimating the phase identity and approximate phase compositions for systems where the final phase assemblage requires estimation.

where the column dimension of \mathbf{C} is greater than or equal to its row dimension. The matrix \mathbf{C} may be partitioned as $[\mathbf{C}_f | \mathbf{C}_e]$, and Equation (1.10) can be re-written

$$\mathbf{n}_c = \mathbf{C}_f \mathbf{n}_f + \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{n}_e \quad (1.11)$$

Note that \mathbf{n}_ϕ , the vector of mole numbers of all phases in the system², is partitioned as $[\mathbf{n}_f \quad \mathbf{n}_e]^T$. The matrix \mathbf{C}_f may have rank less than f . Any number of situations can generate this rank deficiency, including imposing a collection of fixed phases whose compositions are redundant, such as multiple structural forms of the same stoichiometry. The transpose of the matrix \mathbf{C}_f may be rendered into the product of three matrices using Singular Value Decomposition [Lawson and Hanson, 1974], as:

$$\mathbf{C}_f^T = \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{S}_f \mathbf{V}_f^T \quad (1.12)$$

where \mathbf{U}_f and \mathbf{V}_f are square orthogonal matrices and \mathbf{S}_f is a diagonal-dominant rectangular matrix; the number of non-zero diagonal elements of \mathbf{S}_f is equal to the rank, r , of \mathbf{C}_f . The columns of \mathbf{V}_f , which are ordered to pair with the diagonal elements of \mathbf{S}_f , partition into an r column range space and $f - r$ column null space:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{11} & \cdots & v_{1r} & v_{1r+1} & \cdots & v_{1f} \\ \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ v_{k1} & \cdots & v_{kr} & v_{kr+1} & \cdots & v_{kf} \\ \vdots & \cdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ v_{c1} & \cdots & v_{cr} & v_{cr+1} & \cdots & v_{cf} \end{bmatrix} = [\mathbf{v}_1 \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{v}_r \quad \mathbf{v}_{r+1} \quad \cdots \quad \mathbf{v}_f] = [\mathbf{V}_{f|r} \quad \mathbf{V}_{f|f}] \quad (1.13)$$

The range space defines the set of linear combinations of system component mole numbers that are free to assume any value in order to accommodate the forced equilibration of the system with the f fixed phases. The null space defines those linear combinations of system component mole numbers are fixed — i.e., that are independent of any mass transfer associated with bringing the system into equilibrium with the imposed assemblage. If \mathbf{b}_c denotes a vector of mole numbers of system components, then if \mathbf{b}_c is substituted for the left hand side of (1.11),

$$\mathbf{b}_c = \mathbf{C}_f \mathbf{n}_f + \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{n}_e \quad (1.14)$$

and both sides of the expression are multiplied by $\mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T$, the result is a set of constraints that permit partial mass exchange according to the stoichiometry of the fixed phase constraints, yet maintain initial system composition in the null space of those phase constraints:

$$\mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{b}_c = \mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{C}_f \mathbf{n}_f + \mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{n}_e \quad (1.15)$$

At this point a brief concrete example is welcome and illustrative.

1.2 Example of phase constraints

Consider a chemical system with thermodynamic components SiO₂, Al₂O₃, CaO, Na₂O and K₂O. For this system we are interested in phase equilibria at some specified temperature and pressure assuming that both quartz (SiO₂) and corundum (Al₂O₃) are present in the system. In addition, the system is known to contain a silicate liquid. We do not know the composition of the silicate liquid, but we have a thermodynamic model that describes its Gibbs free energy of this solution in terms of components SiO₂, Al₂O₃, CaSiO₃, Na₂SiO₃, KAlSiO₄. The system is free to exchange both SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ with its surroundings to alter the initially specified bulk composition, given by

$$\mathbf{b}_c = [b_{\text{SiO}_2} \quad b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \quad b_{\text{CaO}} \quad b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \quad b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}}]^T \quad (1.16)$$

² If a phase is a solution, there is an entry in the vector for each end member component of that solution.

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in order to bring the system to equilibrium with quartz and corundum at the specified temperature and pressure.

Equation (1.14) may be written for this case as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{Qz} \\ n_{Cr} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.17)$$

and Equation (1.12) becomes:

$$\mathbf{C}_f^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{S}_f \mathbf{V}_f^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.18)$$

from which

$$\mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.19)$$

Multiplying Equation (1.16) by Equation (1.18) gives

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{Qz} \\ n_{Cr} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.20)$$

which simplified to

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{Qz} \\ n_{Cr} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.21)$$

Equation (1.21) is a concrete example of Equation (1.15). Note that the final set of constraints do not involve the initial concentrations of SiO₂ or Al₂O₃ in the system, which is consistent with the open system nature of the phase present constraints.

To complete this example, note the the Khorzhinskii potential, Equation (1.8), would be written:

$$L(T, P, n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}, n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}) = G - n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \quad (1.22)$$

and that to compute thermodynamic equilibrium, this function would be minimized subject to constant temperature, pressure, and

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{Qz} \\ n_{Cr} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (1.23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - \mu_{Qz}^o &= 0 \\ \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} - \mu_{Cr}^o &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, note that because the liquid is an omnicomponent phase, the system chemical potentials can be written in terms of liquid components:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_{\text{SiO}_2} &= \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\
 \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} &= \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\
 \mu_{\text{CaO}} &= \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\
 \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} &= \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\
 \mu_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} &= 2\mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} - 2\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.24}$$

In the next section, we consider numerical methods of performing this minimization.

1.3 Minimizing the generalized potential

Equation (1.8) is a non-linear function of T , P , and \mathbf{n}_ϕ . At constant temperature and pressure, an equilibrium system may be found by minimizing this equation with respect to all \mathbf{n}_ϕ subject to all relevant statements of Equation (1.5) and to Equation (1.15). This problem is one of non-linear optimization subject to non-linear constraints. There are numerous methods for computing numerical solutions to this problem. One of the computationally fastest and proven methods (Ghiorso and Kelemen, 1987) is based on a second-order Newton iterative technique that employs explicit second-order derivatives.

We transform Equation (1.8) to its Lagrangian form

$$\Lambda = G - \sum_j^f \left(\mathbf{R}_{\phi_j}^T \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{n}_\phi \right) \left(\mathbf{R}_{\phi_j}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} \right) - \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{n_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{n_{c-f}} \end{bmatrix}^T \left(\mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{n}_\phi - \mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{b}_c \right) - \sum_j^f \lambda_{\phi_j} \left(\mathbf{R}_{\phi_j}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} - \mu_{\phi_j} \right) \tag{1.25}$$

by introducing Lagrange multipliers, λ_{n_1} to $\lambda_{n_{c-f}}$ and λ_{ϕ_1} to λ_{ϕ_f} whose values are never negative and should tend towards zero as the minimum of Λ is achieved. The third, fourth and fifth terms of Equation (1.25) derive from the equality constraints. These equality constraints can be rearranged into a zero vector of length c :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{C}_e \mathbf{n}_\phi - \mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{b}_c \\ \sum_k^c c_{\phi_1 k} \mu_k - \mu_{\phi_1} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_k^c c_{\phi_f k} \mu_k - \mu_{\phi_f} \end{bmatrix} \tag{1.26}$$

This vector can be differentiated with respect to the mole numbers of phases in the system to define a “linearized” constraint matrix, \mathbf{A} ,

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_e^T \mathbf{V}_{f|f} \\ \sum_k^c c_{\phi_1 k} \frac{\partial \mu_k}{\partial \mathbf{n}_c} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_k^c c_{\phi_f k} \frac{\partial \mu_k}{\partial \mathbf{n}_c} \end{bmatrix} \tag{1.27}$$

The dimensions of \mathbf{A} are $c - r + f$ rows and p columns. A matrix \mathbf{Z} can be computed from \mathbf{A} using either orthogonal or singular value decomposition that has the property of projecting the optimal parameters, \mathbf{n}_ϕ , into the “linearized” null space of the constraints. The elements of \mathbf{Z} are themselves functions of \mathbf{n}_ϕ because the last f rows of \mathbf{A} depend explicitly on \mathbf{n}_ϕ . This is what makes the constraints non-linear in the optimal parameters. Nevertheless, \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{Z} can be applied to embody the non-linear constraints in an approximate fashion in order to develop an algorithm to compute the minimum of Λ .

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Choose some initial guess for the minimum of Λ that satisfies the equality constraints and call it \mathbf{n}_ϕ^i . Define a vector of differences, $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i$, so that a better estimate for the minimum is given by $\mathbf{n}_\phi^{i+1} = \Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$. Applying the null space projection operator obtained from the linearized equality constraints,

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n}_\phi^{i+1} = \mathbf{Z}\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{n}_\phi^i \quad (1.28)$$

Λ may now be expanded in a Taylor series, as:

$$\Lambda_{i+1} = \Lambda_i + \mathbf{g}^T \mathbf{Z} \Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i + (\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i)^T \mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{Z} \Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \dots \quad (1.29)$$

In Equation (1.29) \mathbf{g} is the gradient of L with respect to \mathbf{n}_ϕ evaluated at \mathbf{n}_ϕ^i and \mathbf{W} is a matrix of second derivatives of Λ with respect to \mathbf{n}_ϕ again evaluated at \mathbf{n}_ϕ^i . This matrix is known as the Wronskian. Truncating the Taylor expansion after the quadratic term, differentiating the result with respect to \mathbf{n}_ϕ^{i+1} and setting the resultant expression to zero, results in:

$$\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{Z} \Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i = -\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{g} \quad (1.30)$$

Evaluation of \mathbf{W} require estimates of the Lagrange multipliers. These estimates are provided by solving the system of equations:

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{A}^T \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{n_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{n_{c-f}} \\ \lambda_{\phi_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{\phi_f} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.31)$$

The numerical solution to Equation (1.30), $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i$ is the quadratic approximation to the minimum of Λ . $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$ is not expected to yield the optimal solution, and in general $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i$ does not result in an incremental approximation to the optimum that is feasible in light of the constraints. This is because the constraints have been linearized in order to compute $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i$, and that linearization is exact only for infinitesimal values of $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i$. Furthermore, the quadratic approximation to the minimum may require scaling to better locate a more optimal approximation to the minimum, and usually this is accomplished by taking some step length, s , along the search direction, as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\phi^{i+1} = s\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^{corr} \quad (1.32)$$

where $\Delta\mathbf{n}_\phi^{corr}$ is a correction term that adjusts the result ($\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\phi^{i+1}$) to maintain feasibility of the constraints, i.e. Equation \ref{eq:27}. The correction term is generally small and must be computed iteratively.

Part II

Case Studies - Theory

CASE STUDIES

In this section we present a few illustrations of solving various phase-constrained equilibrium calculations using the methods developed above.

2.1 Pure phase constraints

Jupyter notebook implementation

Follow this [link](#) to a Jupyter notebook that implements this example.

We first consider the simple case explored previously involving two pure phases, quartz and corundum, in equilibrium with a silicate liquid. The Gibbs free energy of this system is given by:

$$G = n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \quad (2.1)$$

and from Equation (1.22) the Khorzhinskii potential is:

$$L = n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} - n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \quad (2.2)$$

Equation (2.2) may be simplified to:

$$L = n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \quad (2.3)$$

We now have a working definition for the Khorzhinskii potential.

In order to construct the Lagrangian associated with this potential, we first simply the equality constraint vector derived previously (Eq. (1.23)) by multiplying out the matrices and substituting liquid potentials for those of the system:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} - b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} - b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} - b_{\text{CaO}} \\ \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Qz}}^o \\ \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Cr}}^o \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

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The matrix \mathbf{A} is the derivative of this vector with respect to $n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}, n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}$:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

and the gradient, \mathbf{g} , of Equation (2.2) is:

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{dL}{d\mathbf{n}_\phi} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

From Eq (2.6), the Hessian of the Khorzhinskii function is

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{d^2L}{d\mathbf{n}_\phi^2} = \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j}$$

The Lagrange multiplier may now be obtained by solving Equation (1.31) using both Equation (2.5) and Equation (2.6) evaluated at an initial guess to the solution. How is this initial guess obtained? By specifying an initial system bulk composition, \mathbf{b}_c , and assigning that composition entirely to the liquid phase, at which point concentrations of $n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}$ and $n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}$ are adjusted to satisfy the equalities $\mu_{Qz}^o = \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}$ and $\mu_{Cr}^o = \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}$. Once the multipliers are computed the Lagrangian function,

$$\Lambda = n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} - \lambda_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \left(\frac{1}{2} n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} - b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \left(n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} - b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{CaO}} \left(n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} - b_{\text{CaO}} \right) \quad (2.7)$$

may be evaluated and its Hessian computed by taking the second partial derivatives with respect to $n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}, n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}$. For this purpose, Equation (2.7) is written more compactly as

$$\Lambda = L - \lambda_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \left(\frac{1}{2} n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} - b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \left(n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} - b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{CaO}} \left(n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} - b_{\text{CaO}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{Qz}} \left(\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Qz}}^o \right) - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \left(\mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Cr}}^o \right) \quad (2.8)$$

and its first derivative with respect to \mathbf{n}_ϕ is

$$\frac{d\Lambda}{d\mathbf{n}_\phi} = \frac{dL}{d\mathbf{n}_\phi} + \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda_{\text{Qz}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ -\lambda_{\text{Qz}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ -\lambda_{\text{CaO}} - \lambda_{\text{Qz}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ -\lambda_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} - \lambda_{\text{Qz}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}} \\ -\lambda_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} - \lambda_{\text{Qz}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.9)$$

which yields a second derivative

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Lambda}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} = \frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{\text{Qz}} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{\text{Cr}} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \quad (2.10)$$

The elements of the Hessian are given by Equation (2.10).

In order to compute a search direction according to Equation (1.30) the orthogonal null space projection matrix, \mathbf{Z} , must be computed from \mathbf{A} . Previously we obtained a similar matrix to project the equality constraints by employing Singular Value Decomposition. That numerical technique is computationally costly, and its use is acceptable because the projection only needed to be applied once for the problem at hand. However, \mathbf{A} must be evaluated and decomposed numerous times in the course of minimizing the Lagrangian, so the fastest possible numerical algorithm should be employed. The preferred method is RQ decomposition, which factors the matrix into the product:

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{RQ} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{11} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_1 \\ \mathbf{Q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.11)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{Q} is orthonormal ($\mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{I}$) and \mathbf{R} is upper triangular. From Equation (2.11) it follows that $\mathbf{Q}_2^T \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{0}$, and consequently that \mathbf{Q}_2^T is the \mathbf{Z} matrix that we seek.

2.2 Fixed chemical potential of oxygen and water

Jupyter notebook implementation

Follow this [link](#) to a Jupyter notebook that implements this example.

Next we consider a silicate liquid in the system $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$. The problem is similar to the one in the previous section, except that it is assumed that an $\text{O}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ fluid phase is not saturated. The Gibbs free energy of this system is written as:

$$G = n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \quad (2.12)$$

from which the Khorzhinskii potential is formally given by

$$L = n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{liq}} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \quad (2.13)$$

Because the system is not saturated with either pure O_2 gas, pure H_2O fluid, or a mixed $\text{H}_2\text{O-O}_2$ fluid, mass balance considerations demand that $n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} = n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sys}}$ and $\frac{1}{2} n_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{sys}} = n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} - n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}$. The equality constraints corresponding to this scenario can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{FeO}} \\ b_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & -4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{sys}} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sys}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.14)$$

where the last two rows account for the additional mass balance constraints. The fixed constraints may be decomposed using SVD as in Equation (1.18)

$$\mathbf{C}_f^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 & -4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{S}_f \mathbf{V}_f^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2\sqrt{5} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & -\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.15)$$

yielding

$$V_{f|f}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.16)$$

Multiplication of the constraint equation by this null-space projection operator gives

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{FeO}} \\ b_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & -4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.17)$$

and finally the projected bulk composition constraint matrix that we seek:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} b_{\text{FeO}} \\ b_{\text{SiO}_2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.18)$$

The complete constraint vector is constructed by stacking this projection along with the fixed external constraints, e.g. Equation (1.23)

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} b_{\text{FeO}} \\ b_{\text{SiO}_2} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0} \quad (2.19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} &= 0 \\ 2\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + 2\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} - 2\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

The last two rows of constraints reflect the fact that there is only one phase in the system, liquid. From Equation (1.23), the \mathbf{A} matrix may be derived

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} \\ -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.20)$$

Note that the entries for the \mathbf{A} matrix in the fourth row may be computed using the definition of the liquid chemical potential of oxygen:

$$\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} = 2 \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} + 2 \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} - 2 \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} \quad (2.21)$$

The gradient of the Khorzhinskii potential is computed from Equation (2.13) as

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{n}_\phi} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.22)$$

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

$$\mathbf{g} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{n}_\phi} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -4\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} - 4\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + 4\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ -4\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} - 4\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + 4\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ 4\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + 4\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - 4\mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ -\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}} + 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}} - 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}} \\ 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}} + 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}} - 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}} \\ 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}} + 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}} - 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}} \\ 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} + 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} - 2\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \end{bmatrix} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}} \\ \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$g_i = \frac{\partial L}{\partial n_i} = \mu_i^{liq} - \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \frac{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i}$$

and the Hessian elements are given by

$$H_{i,j} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} = \frac{\partial \mu_i^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \frac{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j}$$

and the Lagrangian is given by:

$$\Lambda = L - \lambda_{\text{Fe}_{Tot}} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} n_{\text{FeO}}^{liq} \right) - \lambda_{\text{SiO}_2} (n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - b_{\text{SiO}_2}) - \lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O},\mu} (\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys}) - \lambda_{\text{O}_2,\mu} (\mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}) \quad (2.23)$$

from which

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial n_i} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial n_i} - \lambda_{\text{Fe}_{Tot}} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \delta_{i,\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \delta_{i,\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4} \right) - \lambda_{\text{SiO}_2} \delta_{i,\text{SiO}_2} - \lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O},\mu} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \lambda_{\text{O}_2,\mu} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \quad (2.24)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Lambda}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O},\mu} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{\text{O}_2,\mu} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \quad (2.25)$$

2.3 Fixed saturation with a solid solution

Jupyter notebook implementation

Follow this [link](#) to a Jupyter notebook that implements this example.

We next consider the case of one pure phase, quartz, and a solid solution, feldspar, in equilibrium with a silicate liquid. The Gibbs free energy of this system is given by

$$G = G^{liq} (n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}, n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}) \quad (2.26)$$

and the Khorzhinskii potential by

$$L = G^{liq} (n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}, n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq}, n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq}) - n_{\text{Qz}}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Qz}}^{liq} - n_{\text{Ab}}^{liq} \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{liq} - n_{\text{An}}^{liq} \Omega_{\text{An}}^{liq} - n_{\text{Sn}}^{liq} \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{liq} \quad (2.27)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{liq} &= \frac{5}{2} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ \Omega_{\text{An}}^{liq} &= \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{liq} &= 2\mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + \mu_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Ab}}^{liq} &= \frac{5}{2} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2} n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2} n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{An}}^{liq} &= n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2} n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Sn}}^{liq} &= 2n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

The equality constraint matrix for this problem is

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 3 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 1 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Qz}}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Ab}}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{An}}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Sn}}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.29)$$

and the decomposition of the “fixed” constraint partition of the constraint matrix is given by:

$$\mathbf{C}_f^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 3 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 2 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 3 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{S}_f \mathbf{V}_f^T = \mathbf{U}_f \begin{bmatrix} x & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x & x & x & x & x \\ x & x & x & x & x \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x & x \\ x & x & x & x & x \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.30)$$

where x denotes some non-zero entry. The null space projection operator applied to the constraint matrix, Equation (2.28), gives:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.31)$$

which simplifies to

$$\frac{1}{2} (b_{\text{CaO}} + b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} + b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} - b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{liq} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.32)$$

or simply the one constraint:

$$\frac{1}{2} (b_{\text{CaO}} + b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} + b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} - b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}) = \frac{1}{2} (n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}) \quad (2.33)$$

The complete set of constraints is now written:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} (n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{liq} - n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}) - \frac{1}{2} (b_{\text{CaO}} + b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} + b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} - b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}) &= 0 \\ \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{qtz} &= 0 \\ \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{plag} &= 0 \\ \Omega_{\text{An}}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{An}}^{plag} &= 0 \\ \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{liq} - \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{plag} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.34)$$

Even without formally writing down definitions of the \mathbf{A} matrix, gradient vector or the Lagrangian, it follows that if the chemical of the feldspars is specified as a constraint as in Equation (2.34), then the solution is uniquely determined without the need for potential minimization.

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

The gradient of the Khorzhinskii potential is computed from Equation (2.27) as

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial n_i} = \frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i} - \frac{\partial n_{Qz}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \mu_{Qz}^{liq} - n_{Qz}^{liq} \frac{\partial \mu_{Qz}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \frac{\partial n_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \Omega_{Ab}^{liq} - n_{Ab}^{liq} \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \frac{\partial n_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \Omega_{An}^{liq} - n_{An}^{liq} \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \frac{\partial n_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \Omega_{Sn}^{liq} - n_{Sn}^{liq} \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \quad (2.35)$$

The Lagrangian function is:

$$\Lambda = L - \lambda_b \left[\frac{1}{2} (n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq} + n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq} - n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}) - \frac{1}{2} (b_{CaO} + b_{Na_2O} + b_{K_2O} - b_{Al_2O_3}) \right] - \lambda_{Qz} (\mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} - \mu_{SiO_2}^{qtz}) - \lambda_{Ab}^{fld} (\Omega_{Ab}^{liq} - \mu_{Ab}^{fld}) - \dots \quad (2.36)$$

which has a gradient:

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial n_i} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial n_i} - \lambda_b \frac{1}{2} (\delta_{i,CaSiO_3}^{liq} + \delta_{i,Na_2SiO_3}^{liq} - \delta_{i,Al_2O_3}^{liq}) - \lambda_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \lambda_{Ab}^{fld} \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \lambda_{An}^{fld} \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - \lambda_{Sn}^{fld} \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} \quad (2.37)$$

from which the elements of the second derivative are:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Lambda}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} = \frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{Qz} \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{Ab}^{fld} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{An}^{fld} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \lambda_{Sn}^{fld} \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \quad (2.38)$$

Part III

Case Studies - Notebooks

CASE STUDIES

In this section we present implementations of the case studies discussed above using Python in Jupyter notebooks.

3.1 Pure phase constraints

Notebook to illustrate the calculation of forcing a silicate liquid to be in equilibrium with both quartz and corundum at a specified temperature and pressure

```
import numpy as np
import scipy.optimize as opt
import scipy.linalg as lin
from thermoengine import model, phases
```

```
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/numdifftools/multicomplex.
↳py:35: DeprecationWarning: `finfo.machar` is deprecated (NumPy 1.22)
_TINY = np.finfo(float).machar.tiny
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/numdifftools/extrapolation.
↳py:9: DeprecationWarning: Please use `convolve1d` from the `scipy.ndimage`
↳namespace, the `scipy.ndimage.filters` namespace is deprecated.
from scipy.ndimage.filters import convolve1d
```

```
thermoDB = model.Database()
quartz = thermoDB.get_phase('Qz')
corundum = thermoDB.get_phase('Crn')
liquid = thermoDB.get_phase('Liq')
```

```
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
```

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Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

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```
self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phas_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phas_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phas_info, ignore_index=True)
```

Set number of components in the system and the number of fixed phases

```
c = 5
f = 2
```

The amount of quartz and corundum in the system is arbitrary so, we fix the amount of each phase at a constant value

```
nPhaseFix = 1.0
```

Choose an initial bulk composition for the silicate liquid. The initial composition listed below is a high-silica rhyolite projected into the system SiO₂-Al₂O₃-CaO-Na₂O-K₂O

```
nc = liquid.endmember_num
bc = np.zeros((c,1))
def setBulkComposition(nSiO2=0.665792, nAl2O3=0.042436, nQz=nPhaseFix, nCr=nPhaseFix):
    bc[0] = nSiO2 + 0.004596 + 0.038493 + 0.062105 + nQz # SiO2 = SiO2 + CaSiO3 +
↳Na2SiO3 + KAlSiO4
    bc[1] = nAl2O3 + 0.062105/2.0 + nCr # Al2O3 = Al2O3 + KAlSiO4/2
    bc[2] = 0.004596 # CaO = CaSiO3
    bc[3] = 0.038493 # Na2O = Na2SiO3
    bc[4] = 0.062105/2.0 # K2O = KAlSiO4/2
m = np.zeros(nc)
def setMoles(nSiO2=0.665792, nAl2O3=0.042436):
    nLiq = np.zeros((c,1))
    nLiq[0] = nSiO2
    nLiq[1] = nAl2O3
    nLiq[2] = 0.004596
    nLiq[3] = 0.038493
    nLiq[4] = 0.062105
    m[0] = nLiq[0] # SiO2
    m[1] = 0.0 # TiO2
    m[2] = nLiq[1] # Al2O3
    m[3] = 0.0 # Fe2O3
    m[4] = 0.0 # Cr2O3
    m[5] = 0.0 # Fe2SiO4
    m[6] = 0.0 # Mn2SiO4
    m[7] = 0.0 # Mg2SiO4
    m[8] = 0.0 # NiSi1/2O2
    m[9] = 0.0 # CoSi1/2O2
    m[10] = nLiq[2] # CaSiO3
    m[11] = nLiq[3] # Na2SiO3
    m[12] = nLiq[4] # KAlSiO4
    m[13] = 0.0 # Ca3(PO4)2
    m[14] = 0.0 # H2O
    return nLiq
```

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Choose a temperature and pressure. Note that the thermodynamic properties of quartz are only functions of temperature and pressure

```
t = 1100.0 # K
p = 1750.0 # bars
mu0Qz = quartz.gibbs_energy(t, p)
mu0Cr = corundum.gibbs_energy(t, p)
```

Find an initial guess that is consistent with the constraints

```
def fcon(x):
    setMoles(nSiO2=x[0], nAl2O3=x[1])
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    return (mu0Qz-muLiq[0])**2 + (mu0Cr-muLiq[2])**2
result = opt.minimize(fcon,np.array([0.665792, 0.042436]))
print (result)
nLiqSiO2 = result.x[0]
nLiqAl2O3 = result.x[1]
nQz = nPhaseFix
nCr = nPhaseFix
setBulkComposition(nSiO2=nLiqSiO2, nAl2O3=nLiqAl2O3, nQz=nQz, nCr=nCr)
print (bc)
```

```
fun: 3.684107884020587e-05
hess_inv: array([[2.31491515e-08, 3.75094508e-09],
 [3.75094508e-09, 6.32655990e-10]])
jac: array([-0.11409814, 6.61904189])
message: 'Desired error not necessarily achieved due to precision loss.'
nfev: 96
nit: 15
njev: 28
status: 2
success: False
x: array([0.6383143 , 0.10639229])
[[1.7435083 ]
 [1.13744479]
 [0.004596 ]
 [0.038493 ]
 [0.0310525 ]]
```

Set up constraint matrix - matrix is constant.

Columns: nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, nQz, nCr Rows: SiO2, Al2O3, CaO, Na2O, K2O

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{Qz}} \\ n_{\text{Cr}} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
C = np.array([[1,0,1,1,1,1,0],[0,1,0,0,0.5,0,1],[0,0,1,0,0,0,0],[0,0,0,1,0,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0.5,0,0]])
```

... and project it into the null space of fixed constraints - yields a constant matrix

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```
CTf = C[:,c:].transpose()
U,S,VT = np.linalg.svd(CTf)
rank = np.count_nonzero(S)
VTff = VT[rank:,:]
Cproj = np.matmul(VTff, C)
print (Cproj)
bcproj = np.matmul(VTff, bc)
print (bcproj)
```

```
[[0.  0.  1.  0.  0.  0.  0. ]
 [0.  0.  0.  1.  0.  0.  0. ]
 [0.  0.  0.  0.  0.5 0.  0. ]]
[[0.004596 ]
 [0.038493 ]
 [0.0310525]]
```

Define the Khorzhinski potential function and its gradient

$$L = G^{liq} + n_{Qz} (\mu_{Qz}^o - \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}) + n_{Cr} (\mu_{Cr}^o - \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq})$$

```
def Khorzhinskii(nQz=nPhaseFix, nCr=nPhaseFix, nLiqSiO2=0.665792, nLiqAl2O3=0.042436,
    t=1100.0, p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nLiqSiO2,nLiqAl2O3) # fills m array
    Gliq = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m)
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    muLiqSiO2 = muLiq[0]
    muLiqAl2O3 = muLiq[2]
    result = Gliq + nQz*(mu0Qz-muLiqSiO2) + nCr*(mu0Cr-muLiqAl2O3)
    return result
```

Define the gradient of the Khorzhinskii potential

$$\mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{SiO_2}^{liq}} - n_{Cr} \frac{\partial \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{SiO_2}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}} - n_{Cr} \frac{\partial \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{CaSiO_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Qz}^o - \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Cr}^o - \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
def Gradient(nQz=nPhaseFix, nCr=nPhaseFix, nLiqSiO2=0.665792, nLiqAl2O3=0.042436,
    t=1100.0, p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nLiqSiO2,nLiqAl2O3) # fills m array
    dgdM = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':1})[0]
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)
    d2gdM2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    result = np.zeros((c+f,1))
    result[0] = dgdM[0] - nQz*d2gdM2[0, 0] - nCr*d2gdM2[0, 2]
    result[1] = dgdM[2] - nQz*d2gdM2[2, 0] - nCr*d2gdM2[2, 2]
    result[2] = dgdM[10]
    result[3] = dgdM[11]
    result[4] = dgdM[12]
```

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```
result[5] = mu0Qz - d2gdm[0]
result[6] = mu0Cr - d2gdm[2]
return result
```

Define a function to compute the “A” constraint matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

```
def Amatrix(nLiqSiO2=0.665792, nLiqAl2O3=0.042436, t=1100.0, p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3) # fills m array
    d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    bottom = np.zeros((2*f, c+f))
    bottom[0][0] = d2gdm2[0, 0]
    bottom[0][1] = d2gdm2[0, 2]
    bottom[0][2] = d2gdm2[0, 10]
    bottom[0][3] = d2gdm2[0, 11]
    bottom[0][4] = d2gdm2[0, 12]
    bottom[1][0] = d2gdm2[2, 0]
    bottom[1][1] = d2gdm2[2, 2]
    bottom[1][2] = d2gdm2[2, 10]
    bottom[1][3] = d2gdm2[2, 11]
    bottom[1][4] = d2gdm2[2, 12]
    bottom[2][5] = 1.0
    bottom[3][6] = 1.0
    result = np.vstack((Cproj, bottom))
    return result
```

Define the Lagrangian of the Khorzhimskii function

$$\Lambda = G^{\text{liq}} - \lambda_{1:f}^T (\mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{Cn} - \mathbf{V}_{f|f}^T \mathbf{b}) + (n_{Qz} - \lambda_{Qz}) (\mu_{Qz}^o - \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}) + (n_{Cr} - \lambda_{Cr}) (\mu_{Cr}^o - \mu_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}) - \lambda_{n_{Qz}} (n_{Qz} - 1) - \lambda_{n_{Cr}} (n_{Cr} - 1)$$

```
def Lagrangian(nQz=nPhaseFix, nCr=nPhaseFix, nLiqSiO2=0.665792, nLiqAl2O3=0.042436,
    t=1100.0, p=1750.0):
    nFix = np.empty((f, 1))
    nFix[0] = nQz
    nFix[1] = nCr
    nLiq = setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3)
    n = np.vstack((nLiq, nFix))
    Gliq = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m)
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    muLiqSiO2 = muLiq[0]
    muLiqAl2O3 = muLiq[2]
    result = Gliq + nQz*(mu0Qz - muLiqSiO2) + nCr*(mu0Cr - muLiqAl2O3)
    # now add the Lagrange terms
    temp = np.matmul(Cproj, n)
    temp = np.subtract(temp, bcproj)
    result -= (np.dot(temp.transpose(), xLambda[0:3])[0][0])
```

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```

result -= xLambda[3][0]*(mu0Qz-muLiqSiO2)
result -= xLambda[4][0]*(mu0Cr-muLiqAl2O3)
result -= xLambda[5][0]*(nQz-1.0)
result -= xLambda[6][0]*(nCr-1.0)
return result

```

Define the Wronskian of the Lagrangian function. Elements of the Wronskian are given by

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Lambda}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} = \frac{\partial^2 G^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{Qz}}{\partial n_i} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{Qz}}{\partial n_j} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - (n_{Qz} - \lambda_{Qz}) \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{Cr}}{\partial n_i} \frac{\partial \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - \frac{\partial n_{Cr}}{\partial n_j} \frac{\partial \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - (n_{Cr} - \lambda_{Cr}) \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j}$$

```

def Wronskian(nQz=nPhaseFix, nCr=nPhaseFix, nLiqSiO2=0.665792, nLiqAl2O3=0.042436,
↳t=1100.0, p=1750.0):
    w = np.zeros((c+f,c+f))

    d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    w[0][0] = d2gdm2[ 0,  0] # liq SiO2, SiO2
    w[0][1] = d2gdm2[ 0,  2] # liq SiO2, Al2O3
    w[0][2] = d2gdm2[ 0, 10] # liq SiO2, CaSiO3
    w[0][3] = d2gdm2[ 0, 11] # liq SiO2, Na2SiO3
    w[0][4] = d2gdm2[ 0, 12] # liq SiO2, KAlSiO4
    w[0][5] = -d2gdm2[ 0,  0] # liq SiO2, quartz
    w[0][6] = -d2gdm2[ 2,  0] # liq SiO2, corundum
    w[1][1] = d2gdm2[ 2,  2] # liq Al2O3, Al2O3
    w[1][2] = d2gdm2[ 2, 10] # liq Al2O3, CaSiO3
    w[1][3] = d2gdm2[ 2, 11] # liq Al2O3, Na2SiO3
    w[1][4] = d2gdm2[ 2, 12] # liq Al2O3, KAlSiO4
    w[1][5] = -d2gdm2[ 0,  2] # liq Al2O3, quartz
    w[1][6] = -d2gdm2[ 2,  2] # liq Al2O3, corundum
    w[2][2] = d2gdm2[10, 10] # liq CaSiO3, CaSiO3
    w[2][3] = d2gdm2[10, 11] # liq CaSiO3, Na2SiO3
    w[2][4] = d2gdm2[10, 12] # liq CaSiO3, KAlSiO4
    w[2][5] = -d2gdm2[ 0, 10] # liq CaSiO3, quartz
    w[2][6] = -d2gdm2[ 2, 10] # liq CaSiO3, corundum
    w[3][3] = d2gdm2[11, 11] # liq Na2SiO3, Na2SiO3
    w[3][4] = d2gdm2[11, 12] # liq Na2SiO3, KAlSiO4
    w[3][5] = -d2gdm2[ 0, 11] # liq Na2SiO3, quartz
    w[3][6] = -d2gdm2[ 2, 11] # liq Na2SiO3, corundum
    w[4][4] = d2gdm2[12, 12] # liq KAlSiO4, KAlSiO4
    w[4][5] = -d2gdm2[ 0, 12] # liq KAlSiO4, quartz
    w[4][6] = -d2gdm2[ 2, 12] # liq KAlSiO4, corundum

    d3gdm3 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':3})[0]
    w[0][0] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 0, 0]
    w[0][1] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 0, 2]
    w[0][2] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 0,10]
    w[0][3] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 0,11]
    w[0][4] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 0,12]
    w[1][1] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 2, 2]
    w[1][2] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 2,10]
    w[1][3] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 2,11]
    w[1][4] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0, 2,12]
    w[2][2] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0,10,10]
    w[2][3] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0,10,11]
    w[2][4] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0,10,12]
    w[3][3] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0,11,11]

```

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```

w[3][4] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0,11,12]
w[4][4] -= (nQz-xLambda[3][0])*d3gdm3[0,12,12]

w[0][0] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 0, 0]
w[0][1] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 0, 2]
w[0][2] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 0,10]
w[0][3] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 0,11]
w[0][4] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 0,12]
w[1][1] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 2, 2]
w[1][2] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 2,10]
w[1][3] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 2,11]
w[1][4] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2, 2,12]
w[2][2] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2,10,10]
w[2][3] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2,10,11]
w[2][4] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2,10,12]
w[3][3] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2,11,11]
w[3][4] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2,11,12]
w[4][4] -= (nCr-xLambda[4][0])*d3gdm3[2,12,12]

for i in range(0,c+f):
    for j in range(i+1,c+f):
        w[j][i] = w[i][j]

return w

```

Form the QR decomposition of A. Note that A must be square, so zero filled rows are added

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{QR} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_1 & \mathbf{Q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_1 \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$$

and \mathbf{Q}_2^T is the matrix \mathbf{Z}

```

A = Amatrix(nLiqSiO2=nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3=nLiqAl2O3)
#bottom = np.zeros((f,c+f))
#A = np.vstack((A, bottom))
#Q,R = lin.qr(A,mode='full')
R,Q = lin.rq(A,mode='full')
print ("Q matrix:")
for i in range(0,Q.shape[0]):
    if Q.shape[1] == c+f:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e} {6:10.3e}
↵".format( \
            Q[i][0], Q[i][1], Q[i][2], Q[i][3], Q[i][4], Q[i][5], Q[i][6]))
    elif Q.shape[1] == c:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e}".format( \
            Q[i][0], Q[i][1], Q[i][2], Q[i][3], Q[i][4]))
print ("R matrix:")
for i in range(0,R.shape[0]):
    if R.shape[1] == c+f:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e} {6:10.3e}
↵".format( \
            R[i][0], R[i][1], R[i][2], R[i][3], R[i][4], R[i][5], R[i][6]))
    elif R.shape[1] == c:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e}".format( \
            R[i][0], R[i][1], R[i][2], R[i][3], R[i][4]))
print ("Z matrix")

```

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```
Z = Q[0:0,:].transpose()
for i in range(0,Z.shape[0]):
    if Z.shape[1] == f:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e}".format(Z[i][0], Z[i][1]))
```

```
Q matrix:
 9.487e-01  2.268e-01  2.202e-01 -4.755e-17 -3.430e-20  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 2.227e-01 -1.257e-01 -8.299e-01  4.959e-01  1.165e-16  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
-1.054e-01  2.486e-01  1.979e-01  4.416e-01 -8.324e-01  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 1.386e-01 -2.405e-01 -3.493e-01 -7.077e-01 -5.478e-01  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 1.416e-01 -9.017e-01  3.188e-01  2.413e-01 -8.342e-02  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
-0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00  1.000e+00  0.000e+00
-0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00  1.000e+00
R matrix:
 2.202e-01 -8.299e-01  1.979e-01 -3.493e-01  3.188e-01  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  4.959e-01  4.416e-01 -7.077e-01  2.413e-01  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00 -4.162e-01 -2.739e-01 -4.171e-02  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  4.691e+04  1.189e+04  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00 -1.554e+05  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  1.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  1.000e+00
Z matrix
```

Form the vector of Lagrange multipliers

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{A}^T \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{n_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{n_{c-f}} \\ \lambda_{\phi_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{\phi_f} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
print ("Gradient:")
g = Gradient(nLiqSiO2=nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3=nLiqAl2O3)
for i in range(0,g.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(g[i][0]))
print ("Lambda:")
xLambda = np.linalg.lstsq(A.transpose(),g, rcond=None)[0]
for i in range(0,xLambda.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(xLambda[i][0]))
```

```
Gradient:
-9.767e+05
-1.910e+06
-1.810e+06
-1.862e+06
-2.371e+06
 5.748e-03
 1.949e-03
Lambda:
-7.984e+06
-1.215e+07
-1.770e+07
-2.699e+02
```

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```
-5.600e+01
 5.748e-03
 1.949e-03
```

Compute the Wronskian of the Lagrangian

```
W = Wronskian(nLiqSiO2=nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3=nLiqAl2O3)
for i in range(0,W.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e} {6:10.3e}").
    format(\
        W[i][0], W[i][1], W[i][2], W[i][3], W[i][4], W[i][5], W[i][6]))
```

```
8.170e+03 -2.202e+04 -1.261e+04 -3.034e+04 -2.670e+04 -8.184e+03 2.200e+04
-2.202e+04 1.401e+05 -4.957e+04 -3.753e+04 1.295e+04 2.200e+04 -1.402e+05
-1.261e+04 -4.957e+04 1.973e+06 6.517e+04 2.791e+04 1.259e+04 4.955e+04
-3.034e+04 -3.753e+04 6.517e+04 4.161e+05 1.132e+05 3.033e+04 3.751e+04
-2.670e+04 1.295e+04 2.791e+04 1.132e+05 1.798e+05 2.669e+04 -1.297e+04
-8.184e+03 2.200e+04 1.259e+04 3.033e+04 2.669e+04 0.000e+00 0.000e+00
2.200e+04 -1.402e+05 4.955e+04 3.751e+04 -1.297e+04 0.000e+00 0.000e+00
```

Next project the gradient and the Wronskian. The search direction ($\Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$) is given by

$$\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{Z} \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i = -\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{g}$$

and $\mathbf{n}_\phi^{i+1} = \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$ gives the quadratic approximation to the minimum, which must be adjusted to maintain the non-linear equality constraints

$$\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\phi^{i+1} = s \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^{corr}$$

```
ZTg = np.matmul(Z.transpose(),g)
ZTWZ = np.matmul(Z.transpose(), np.matmul(W,Z))
print("Z^T g")
for i in range(0,ZTg.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(ZTg[i][0]))
print("Z^T W Z")
for i in range(0,ZTWZ.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e}".format(ZTWZ[i][0], ZTWZ[i][1]))
```

```
Z^T g
Z^T W Z
```

... and solve for the correction vector

```
x = lin.solve(ZTWZ, ZTg)
print ("Solution in the null space:")
for i in range(0,x.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(x[i][0]))
deltan = np.matmul(Z,x)
print ("Inflated Solution:")
for i in range(0,deltan.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(deltan[i][0]))
```

```
Solution in the null space:  
Inflated Solution:  
0.000e+00  
0.000e+00  
0.000e+00  
0.000e+00  
0.000e+00  
0.000e+00  
0.000e+00
```

Final solution

The correction vector is zero because the initial guess satisfies all constraints and the number of constraints is equal to the number of unknowns.

```
nLiq = setMoles(nSiO2=nLiqSiO2, nAl2O3=nLiqAl2O3)  
print ("n SiO2    liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[0][0]+deltan[0][0]))  
print ("n Al2O3   liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[1][0]+deltan[1][0]))  
print ("n CaSiO3  liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[2][0]+deltan[2][0]))  
print ("n Na2SiO3 liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[3][0]+deltan[3][0]))  
print ("n KAlSiO4  liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[4][0]+deltan[4][0]))  
print ("n Qz      = {0:8.6f}".format(nQz+deltan[5][0]))  
print ("n Cr      = {0:8.6f}".format(nCr+deltan[6][0]))
```

```
n SiO2    liq = 0.638314  
n Al2O3   liq = 0.106392  
n CaSiO3  liq = 0.004596  
n Na2SiO3 liq = 0.038493  
n KAlSiO4 liq = 0.062105  
n Qz      = 1.000000  
n Cr      = 1.000000
```

3.2 Fixed chemical potential of oxygen and water

Notebook to illustrate the calculation of forcing a silicate liquid to be in equilibrium with specified chemical potentials of oxygen and water, under conditions where neither phase is present in the system

```
import numpy as np  
import scipy.optimize as opt  
import scipy.linalg as lin  
from thermoengine import phases, model
```

```
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/numdifftools/multicomplex.  
↳py:35: DeprecationWarning: `finfo.machar` is deprecated (NumPy 1.22)  
    _TINY = np.finfo(float).machar.tiny  
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/numdifftools/extrapolation.  
↳py:9: DeprecationWarning: Please use `convolve1d` from the `scipy.ndimage` ↵  
↳namespace, the `scipy.ndimage.filters` namespace is deprecated.  
    from scipy.ndimage.filters import convolve1d
```

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

```
modelDB = model.Database(liq_mod='v1.0')
liquid = modelDB.get_phase('Liq')
water = phases.PurePhase('WaterMelts', 'H2O', calib=False)
```

```
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
```

Define a function to calculate the Gibbs free energy of oxygen gas

```
def gOxygen(t, p):
    tr = 298.15
    pr = 1.0
    hs = 23.10248*(t-tr) + 2.0*804.8876*(np.sqrt(t)-np.sqrt(tr)) \
        - 1762835.0*(1.0/t-1.0/tr) \
        - 18172.91960*np.log(t/tr) + 0.5*0.002676*(t*t-tr*tr)
    ss = 205.15 + 23.10248*np.log(t/tr) \
        - 2.0*804.8876*(1.0/np.sqrt(t)-1.0/np.sqrt(tr)) \
        - 0.5*1762835.0*(1.0/(t*t)-1.0/(tr*tr)) \
        + 18172.91960*(1.0/t-1.0/tr) + 0.002676*(t-tr)
    vs = 8.3143*t/pr
    return hs - t*ss
```

Set number of components in the system and the number of fixed phases

```
c = 4
f = 2
```

Choose an initial bulk composition for the silicate liquid. The initial composition listed below is calculated for the early erupted Bishop Tuff.

```
nc = liquid.endmember_num
bc = np.zeros((c,1))
nSiO2    = 0.665792
nTiO2    = 0.000600
nAl2O3   = 0.042436
nFe2O3   = 0.000777
nFe2SiO4 = 0.001973
nMg2SiO4 = 0.000223
nCaSiO3  = 0.004596
nNa2SiO3 = 0.038493
nKAlSiO4 = 0.062105
```

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Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

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```

nH2O      = 0.183006
nFeTot    = 2.0*nFe2O3 + 2.0*nFe2SiO4
def setBulkComposition(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006):
    bc[0] = nSiO2 + nFe2SiO4      # SiO2
    bc[1] = nFe2O3in              # Fe2O3
    bc[2] = nFeTot - 2.0*nFe2O3in # FeO
    bc[3] = nH2Oin                # H2O
m = np.zeros(nc)
def setMoles(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006):
    exSiO2 = nFe2SiO4 - (nFeTot - 2.0*nFe2O3in)
    nLiq = np.zeros((c,1))
    nLiq[0] = nSiO2 + nFe2SiO4 + exSiO2
    nLiq[1] = nFe2O3in
    nLiq[2] = (nFeTot - 2.0*nFe2O3in)/2.0
    nLiq[3] = nH2Oin
    m[0] = nLiq[0] # SiO2
    m[1] = 0.0    # TiO2
    m[2] = 0.0    # Al2O3
    m[3] = nLiq[1] # Fe2O3
    m[4] = 0.0    # Cr2O3
    m[5] = nLiq[2] # Fe2SiO4
    m[6] = 0.0    # Mn2SiO4
    m[7] = 0.0    # Mg2SiO4
    m[8] = 0.0    # NiSi1/2O2
    m[9] = 0.0    # CoSi1/2O2
    m[10] = 0.0   # CaSiO3
    m[11] = 0.0  # Na2SiO3
    m[12] = 0.0  # KAlSiO4
    m[13] = 0.0  # Ca3(PO4)2
    m[14] = nLiq[3] # H2O
    return nLiq

```

Choose a temperature and pressure. Note that the thermodynamic properties of O₂ and H₂O are only functions of temperature and pressure.

```

t = 1053.15 # K
p = 1750.0 # bars
muO2 = gOxygen(t, p)
muOH2O = water.gibbs_energy(t,p)
muO2 = muO2 + (-24930.0/t + 9.360)*np.log(10.0)*8.3143*t # NNO
muH2O = muOH2O + np.log(1.0)*8.3143*t # activity = 0.5

```

Find an initial guess that is consistent with the constraints

```

def gcon(x):
    t0 = 1673.15 # K
    a = 0.196
    b = 1.1492e4 # K
    c = -6.675
    e = -3.364
    f = -7.01e-7 * 1.0e5 # K/bar
    g = -1.54e-10 * 1.0e5 # 1/bar
    h = 3.85e-17 * 1.0e5 * 1.0e5 # K/bar^2
    temp = b/t + c + e*(1.0-t0/t - np.log(t/t0)) + f*p/t + g*(t-t0)*p/t + h*p*p/t
    mSiO2 = nSiO2 + nFe2SiO4 + nMg2SiO4 + nCaSiO3 + nNa2SiO3 + nKAlSiO4

```

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Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

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```
mTiO2 = nTiO2
mAl2O3 = nAl2O3
mFeTot = nFeTot
mMgO = 2.0*nMg2SiO4
mCaO = nCaSiO3
mNa2O = nNa2SiO3
mK2O = nKAlSiO4
mH2O = x[1]
total = mSiO2 + mTiO2 + mAl2O3 + mFeTot + mMgO + mCaO + mNa2O + mK2O + mH2O
dAl2O3 = -2.243
dFeO = -1.828
dCaO = 3.201
dNa2O = 5.854
dK2O = 6.215
temp += dAl2O3*mAl2O3/total + dFeO*mFeTot/total + dCaO*mCaO/total + dNa2O*mNa2O/
↪total + dK2O*mK2O/total
mFe2O3 = x[0]
mFeO = mFeTot - 2.0*mFe2O3
return 8.3143*t*(np.log(mFe2O3/mFeO) - temp)/a + muO2
def fcon(x):
    setMoles(nFe2O3in=x[0], nH2Oin=x[1])
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    if useKressCarmichael:
        zeroMuO2 = muO2 - gcon(x)
        #print (zeroMuO2, muO2)
    else:
        zeroMuO2 = muO2 + 2.0*muLiq[5] - 2.0*muLiq[0] - 2.0*muLiq[3]
        zeroMuH2O = muH2O - muLiq[14]
    return (zeroMuO2)**2 + (zeroMuH2O)**2
useKressCarmichael = 0
result = opt.minimize(fcon,np.array([0.000777, 0.183006]),bounds=((0,nFeTot/2.0),(0,
↪None)))
print (result)
nLiqFe2O3 = result.x[0]
nLiqH2O = result.x[1]
setBulkComposition(nFe2O3in=nLiqFe2O3, nH2Oin=nLiqH2O)
print (bc)
```

```
fun: 0.035204494438985726
hess_inv: <2x2 LbfgsInvHessProduct with dtype=float64>
jac: array([-37.35300474, -0.52325594])
message: 'CONVERGENCE: REL_REDUCTION_OF_F_<= _FACTR*EPSMCH'
nfev: 69
nit: 11
njev: 23
status: 0
success: True
x: array([0.00063729, 0.11701839])
[[6.67765000e-01]
 [6.37290240e-04]
 [4.22541952e-03]
 [1.17018388e-01]]
```

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

Set up constraint matrix - matrix is constant

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{FeO}} \\ b_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 & 0 & -4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \\ n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} \\ n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
C = np.array([[1,0,1,0,0,0],[0,1,0,0,2,0],[0,0,2,0,-4,0],[0,0,0,1,0,1]])
```

... and project it into the null space of fixed constraints - yields a constant matrix

```
CTf = C[:,c:].transpose()
U,S,VT = np.linalg.svd(CTf)
rank = np.count_nonzero(S)
VTff = VT[rank:,:]
Cproj = np.matmul(VTff, C)
print ("Cproj")
for i in range(0,Cproj.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e}".format( \
        Cproj[i][0], Cproj[i][1], Cproj[i][2], Cproj[i][3], Cproj[i][4], Cproj[i][5]))
bcproj = np.matmul(VTff, bc)
print ("bcproj")
for i in range(0,bcproj.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(bcproj[i][0]))
```

```
Cproj
8.944e-01  4.000e-01  1.294e+00  0.000e+00 -2.220e-16  0.000e+00
4.472e-01 -8.000e-01 -3.528e-01  0.000e+00 -2.220e-16  0.000e+00
bcproj
5.984e-01
2.964e-01
```

CTf

```
array([[ 0,  2, -4,  0],
       [ 0,  0,  0,  1]])
```

Define the Khorzhinski potential function and its gradient

$$L = n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} + n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys}$$

```
def Khorzhinskii(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006, t=1053.15, p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nFe2O3in, nH2Oin) # fills m array
    Gliq = liquid.getGibbsFreeEnergyFromMolesOfComponents_andT_andP_(m,t,p)
    result = Gliq - (2.0*m[3]+2.0*m[0]-2.0*m[5])*muO2 - m[14]*muH2O
    return result
```

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

Define the gradient of the Khorzhinskii potential

$$\mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq} \\ \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq} \\ -\mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}} \\ -\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys} \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys}} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
def Gradient(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006, t=1053.15, p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nFe2O3in, nH2Oin) # fills m array
    dgdM = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':1})[0]
    result = np.zeros((c+f,1))
    result[0] = dgdM[0]
    result[1] = dgdM[3]
    result[2] = dgdM[5]
    result[3] = dgdM[14]
    result[4] = -muO2
    result[5] = -muH2O
    return result
```

Define a function to compute the “A” constraint matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{sys}} \\ -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{liq}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}}{\partial n_{\text{O}_2}^{sys}} & 0 \\ -2 & -2 & 2 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} = 2 \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} + 2 \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}} - 2 \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_i^{liq}}$$

```
def Amatrix(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006, t=1053.15, p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nFe2O3in, nH2Oin) # fills m array
    #d2gdm2 = liquid.getD2gDm2FromMolesOfComponents_andT_andP_(m, t, p)
    d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    bottom = np.zeros((2*f,c+f))
    bottom[0][0] = -d2gdm2[14, 0]
    bottom[0][1] = -d2gdm2[14, 3]
    bottom[0][2] = -d2gdm2[14, 5]
    bottom[0][3] = -d2gdm2[14, 14]
    bottom[1][0] = -( 2.0*d2gdm2[0, 0] + 2.0*d2gdm2[3, 0] - 2.0*d2gdm2[5, 0])
    bottom[1][1] = -( 2.0*d2gdm2[0, 3] + 2.0*d2gdm2[3, 3] - 2.0*d2gdm2[5, 3])
    bottom[1][2] = -( 2.0*d2gdm2[0, 5] + 2.0*d2gdm2[3, 5] - 2.0*d2gdm2[5, 5])
    bottom[1][3] = -( 2.0*d2gdm2[0, 14] + 2.0*d2gdm2[3, 14] - 2.0*d2gdm2[5, 14])
    bottom[2][0] = -2.0
    bottom[2][1] = -2.0
    bottom[2][2] = 2.0
    bottom[2][4] = 1.0
    bottom[3][3] = -1.0
    bottom[3][5] = 1.0
```

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```
result = np.vstack((Cproj, bottom))
return result
```

Define the Lagrangian of the Khorzhimskii function

$$\Lambda = n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} + n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} - n_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{sys}} \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{sys}} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sys}} \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sys}} \\ - \lambda_{\text{Fe}_{Tot}} \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} + \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} b_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} n_{\text{FeO}}^{\text{liq}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{SiO}_2} \left(n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} - b_{\text{SiO}_2} \right) \\ - \lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \mu} \left(\mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sys}} - \mu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{O}_2, \mu} \left(\mu_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{sys}} - \mu_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{liq}} \right) \\ - \lambda_{\text{O}_2, n} \left(n_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{sys}} + 2n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{SiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} - 2n_{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} - 2n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \right) - \lambda_{\text{H}_2\text{O}, n} \left(n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{sys}} - n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\text{liq}} \right)$$

```
def Lagrangian(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006, t=1053.15, p=1750.0):
    nLiq = setMoles(nFe2O3in, nH2Oin)
    nFix = np.empty((f, 1))
    nFix[0] = 2.0*nLiq[1]+2.0*nLiq[0]-2.0*nLiq[2]
    nFix[1] = nLiq[3]
    n = np.vstack((nLiq, nFix))
    Gliq = liquid.getGibbsFreeEnergyFromMolesOfComponents_andT_andP_(m, t, p)
    muLiq = liquid.getChemicalPotentialFromMolesOfComponents_andT_andP_(m, t, p)
    result = Gliq - nFix[0]*muO2 - nFix[1]*muH2O
    # now add the Lagrange terms
    temp = np.matmul(Cproj, n)
    temp = np.subtract(temp, bcproj)
    result -= (np.dot(temp.transpose(), xLambda[0:2])[0][0])
    muLiqSiO2 = muLiq.valueAtIndex_(0)
    muLiqFe2O3 = muLiq.valueAtIndex_(3)
    muLiqFe2SiO4 = muLiq.valueAtIndex_(5)
    muLiqH2O = muLiq.valueAtIndex_(14)
    result -= xLambda[2][0]*(muH2O-muLiqH2O)
    result -= xLambda[3][0]*(muO2-(2.0*muLiqFe2O3+2.0*muLiqSiO2-2.0*muLiqFe2SiO4))
    result -= xLambda[4][0]*(nFix[0]-(2.0*nLiq[1]+2.0*nLiq[0]-2.0*nLiq[2]))
    result -= xLambda[5][0]*(nFix[1]-nLiq[3])
    return result
```

Define the Wronskian of the Lagrangian function

```
def Wronskian(nFe2O3in=0.000777, nH2Oin=0.183006, t=1053.15, p=1750.0):
    nLiq = setMoles(nFe2O3in, nH2Oin)
    w = np.zeros((c+f, c+f))

    d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    w[0][0] = d2gdm2[ 0, 0] # liq SiO2, SiO2
    w[0][1] = d2gdm2[ 0, 3] # liq SiO2, Fe2O3
    w[0][2] = d2gdm2[ 0, 5] # liq SiO2, Fe2SiO4
    w[0][3] = d2gdm2[ 0, 14] # liq SiO2, H2O
    w[1][1] = d2gdm2[ 3, 3] # liq Fe2O3, Fe2O3
    w[1][2] = d2gdm2[ 3, 5] # liq Fe2O3, Fe2SiO4
    w[1][3] = d2gdm2[ 3, 14] # liq Fe2O3, H2O
    w[2][2] = d2gdm2[ 5, 5] # liq Fe2SiO4, Fe2SiO4
    w[2][3] = d2gdm2[ 5, 14] # liq Fe2SiO4, H2O
    w[3][3] = d2gdm2[14, 14] # liq H2O, H2O

    d3gdm3 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':3})[0]
    w[0][0] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 0, 0]
    w[0][1] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 0, 3]
```

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```

w[0][2] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 0, 5]
w[0][3] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 0,14]
w[1][1] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 3, 3]
w[1][2] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 3, 5]
w[1][3] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 3,14]
w[2][2] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 5, 5]
w[2][3] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14, 5,14]
w[3][3] += xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3[14,14,14]

w[0][0] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 0, 0]
w[0][1] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 0, 3]
w[0][2] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 0, 5]
w[0][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 0,14]
w[1][1] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 3, 3]
w[1][2] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 3, 5]
w[1][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 3,14]
w[2][2] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 5, 5]
w[2][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0, 5,14]
w[3][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 0,14,14]

w[0][0] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 0, 0]
w[0][1] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 0, 3]
w[0][2] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 0, 5]
w[0][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 0,14]
w[1][1] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 3, 3]
w[1][2] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 3, 5]
w[1][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 3,14]
w[2][2] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 5, 5]
w[2][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3, 5,14]
w[3][3] += 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 3,14,14]

w[0][0] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 0, 0]
w[0][1] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 0, 3]
w[0][2] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 0, 5]
w[0][3] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 0,14]
w[1][1] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 3, 3]
w[1][2] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 3, 5]
w[1][3] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 3,14]
w[2][2] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 5, 5]
w[2][3] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5, 5,14]
w[3][3] -= 2.0*xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3[ 5,14,14]

for i in range(0,c+f):
    for j in range(i+1,c+f):
        w[j][i] = w[i][j]

return w

```

Form the QR decomposition of A. Note that A must be square, so zero filled rows are added.

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{QR} = [\mathbf{Q}_1 \quad \mathbf{Q}_2] \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_1 \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$$

and \mathbf{Q}_2^T is the matrix \mathbf{Z}

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```
A = Amatrix(nFe2O3in=nLiqFe2O3, nH2Oin=nLiqH2O)
#bottom = np.zeros((f,c+f))
#A = np.vstack((A, bottom))
#Q,R = lin.qr(A,mode='full')
R,Q = lin.rq(A,mode='full')
print ("Q matrix:")
for i in range(0,Q.shape[0]):
    if Q.shape[1] == c+f:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e}".format( \
            Q[i][0], Q[i][1], Q[i][2], Q[i][3], Q[i][4], Q[i][5]))
    elif Q.shape[1] == c:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e}".format( \
            Q[i][0], Q[i][1], Q[i][2], Q[i][3], Q[i][4]))
print ("R matrix:")
for i in range(0,R.shape[0]):
    if R.shape[1] == c+f:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e}".format( \
            R[i][0], R[i][1], R[i][2], R[i][3], R[i][4], R[i][5]))
    elif R.shape[1] == c:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e}".format( \
            R[i][0], R[i][1], R[i][2], R[i][3], R[i][4]))
print ("Z matrix")
Z = Q[0:0,:].transpose()
for i in range(0,Z.shape[0]):
    if Z.shape[1] == f:
        print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e}".format(Z[i][0], Z[i][1]))
```

```
Q matrix:
 5.401e-01  1.250e-01  4.012e-01  3.556e-01  5.280e-01  3.556e-01
-4.908e-02  1.483e-01  4.757e-01  3.019e-01 -7.530e-01  3.019e-01
-3.332e-01 -1.685e-01 -5.388e-01  5.314e-01  7.426e-02  5.314e-01
 5.359e-01 -7.914e-01 -1.216e-01 -3.666e-04 -2.679e-01 -3.666e-04
 5.547e-01  5.547e-01 -5.547e-01  0.000e+00 -2.774e-01  0.000e+00
-0.000e+00 -0.000e+00 -0.000e+00  7.071e-01 -0.000e+00 -7.071e-01
R matrix:
 1.052e+00  6.312e-01 -1.063e+00  5.339e-03  1.073e-16  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00 -3.084e-01  1.758e-01  9.157e-01  1.817e-17  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00 -6.625e+04 -1.393e+04 -4.283e+03 -4.978e+04
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  2.106e+07 -2.034e+07 -1.092e+04
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00 -3.606e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00 -1.414e+00
Z matrix
```

Form the vector of Lagrange multipliers

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{A}^T \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{n_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{n_{c-f}} \\ \lambda_{\phi_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{\phi_f} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
print ("Gradient:")
g = Gradient(nFe2O3in=nLiqFe2O3, nH2Oin=nLiqH2O)
for i in range(0,g.shape[0]):
```

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```

print ("{0:10.3e}".format(g[i][0]))
print ("Lambda:")
xLambda = np.linalg.lstsq(A.transpose(),g, rcond=None)[0]
for i in range(0,xLambda.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(xLambda[i][0]))

```

```

Gradient:
-9.823e+05
-1.009e+06
-1.730e+06
-3.978e+05
 5.224e+05
 3.978e+05
Lambda:
-1.021e+06
 2.182e+06
 1.719e-02
-7.835e-02
 5.224e+05
 3.978e+05

```

Compute the Wronskian of the Lagrangian

```

W = Wronskian(nFe2O3in=nLiqFe2O3, nH2Oin=nLiqH2O)
for i in range(0,W.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e} {4:10.3e} {5:10.3e}".format( \
        W[i][0], W[i][1], W[i][2], W[i][3], W[i][4], W[i][5]))

```

```

 6.227e+03 -4.899e+03 -7.129e+02 -1.943e+04  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
-4.899e+03  1.372e+07 -2.673e+05 -2.665e+04  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
-7.129e+02 -2.673e+05  4.090e+06 -4.897e+04  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
-1.943e+04 -2.665e+04 -4.897e+04  6.920e+04  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00
 0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00  0.000e+00

```

Next project the gradient and the Wronskian. The search direction ($\Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$) is given by

$$\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{Z} \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i = -\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{g}$$

and $\mathbf{n}_\phi^{i+1} = \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$ gives the quadratic approximation to the minimum, which must be adjusted to maintain the non-linear equality constraints $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\phi^{i+1} = s \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^{corr}$

```

ZTg = np.matmul(Z.transpose(),g)
ZTWZ = np.matmul(Z.transpose(), np.matmul(W,Z))
print ("Z^T g")
for i in range(0,ZTg.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(ZTg[i][0]))
print ("Z^T W Z")
for i in range(0,ZTWZ.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e}".format(ZTWZ[i][0], ZTWZ[i][1]))

```

```

Z^T g
Z^T W Z

```

... and solve for the correction vector

```
x = lin.solve(ZTWZ, ZTg)
print ("Solution in the null space:")
for i in range(0,x.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(x[i][0]))
deltan = np.matmul(Z,x)
print ("Inflated Solution:")
for i in range(0,deltan.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(deltan[i][0]))
```

```
Solution in the null space:
Inflated Solution:
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
```

Final solution

The correction vector is zero because the initial guess satisfies all constraints and the number of constraints is equal to the number of unknowns.

```
nLiq = setMoles(nFe2O3in=nLiqFe2O3, nH2Oin=nLiqH2O)
print ("n SiO2    liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[0][0]+deltan[0][0]))
print ("n Fe2O3    liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[1][0]+deltan[1][0]))
print ("n Fe2SiO4  liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[2][0]+deltan[2][0]))
print ("n H2O      liq = {0:8.6f}".format(nLiq[3][0]+deltan[3][0]))
```

```
n SiO2    liq = 0.665513
n Fe2O3    liq = 0.000637
n Fe2SiO4  liq = 0.002113
n H2O      liq = 0.117018
```

3.3 Fixed saturation with a solid solution

Notebook to illustrate the calculation of forcing a silicate liquid to be in equilibrium with both quartz, plagioclase and sanidine at a specified temperature and pressure

```
import numpy as np
import scipy.optimize as opt
import scipy.linalg as lin
from thermoengine import model, phases
```

```
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/numdifftools/multicomplex.
↳py:35: DeprecationWarning: `finfo.machar` is deprecated (NumPy 1.22)
    _TINY = np.finfo(float).machar.tiny
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/numdifftools/extrapolation.
↳py:9: DeprecationWarning: Please use `convolve1d` from the `scipy.ndimage`
↳namespace, the `scipy.ndimage.filters` namespace is deprecated.
    from scipy.ndimage.filters import convolve1d
```

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```
modelDB = model.Database()
quartz = modelDB.get_phase('Qz')
liquid = modelDB.get_phase('Liq')
plagioclase = modelDB.get_phase('Fsp')
sanidine = modelDB.get_phase('Fsp')
```

```
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
/Users/ghiorso/mambaforge/lib/python3.9/site-packages/thermoengine/model.py:184:
↳FutureWarning: The frame.append method is deprecated and will be removed from
↳pandas in a future version. Use pandas.concat instead.
    self._phase_info = self._phase_info.append(phs_info, ignore_index=True)
```

Set number of components in the system and the number of fixed phases

```
c = 5
f = 7
```

The amount of quartz in the system is arbitrary so, we fix its amount at a constant value

```
nPhaseFix = 1.0
```

Generate some information about the feldspar solid solution. Set initial composition of plagioclase and sanidine just for testing purposes

```
ncFeldspar = plagioclase.endmember_num
print ('Feldspar: number of solution components = ', ncFeldspar)
mPlag = np.array([0.8, 0.1, 0.1])
mAlk = np.array([0.3, 0.1, 0.6])
for i in range(0,ncFeldspar):
    print ('Component No: {0:1d} is {1:<15s} Initial guess for Plag = {2:5.2f} Alk
↳= {3:5.2f}'.format( \
    i, plagioclase.props['endmember_name'][i], mPlag[i], mAlk[i]))
```

```
Feldspar: number of solution components = 3
Component No: 0 is albite           Initial guess for Plag = 0.80 Alk = 0.30
```

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```
Component No: 1 is anorthite      Initial guess for Plag = 0.10 Alk = 0.10
Component No: 2 is sanidine      Initial guess for Plag = 0.10 Alk = 0.60
```

Choose an initial bulk composition for the silicate liquid. The initial composition listed below is a high-silica rhyolite projected into the system SiO₂-Al₂O₃-CaO-Na₂O-K₂O

```
nc = liquid.endmember_num
bc = np.zeros((c,1))
def setBulkComposition(nSiO2=0.665792, nAl2O3=0.042436, nCaSiO3=0.004596, nNa2SiO3=0.
↪038493, nKAlSiO4=0.062105, \
    nQz=nPhaseFix, nPlagAb=0.8, nPlagAn=0.1, nPlagSn=0.1, nAlkAb=0.
↪3, nAlkAn=0.1, nAlkSn=0.6):
    global bc
    bc[0] = nSiO2 + nCaSiO3 + nNa2SiO3 + nKAlSiO4 + nQz + 3.0*nPlagAb + 2.0*nPlagAn +
↪3.0*nPlagSn \
        + 3.0*nAlkAb + 2.0*nAlkAn + 3.0*nAlkSn
    bc[1] = nAl2O3 + nKAlSiO4/2.0 + nPlagAb/2.0 + nPlagAn + nPlagSn/2.0 + nAlkAb/2.0
↪+ nAlkAn + nAlkSn/2.0
    bc[2] = nCaSiO3 + nPlagAn + nAlkAn
    bc[3] = nNa2SiO3 + nPlagAb/2.0 + nAlkAb/2.0
    bc[4] = nKAlSiO4/2.0 + nPlagSn/2.0 + nAlkSn/2.0
m = np.zeros(nc)
def setMoles(nSiO2=0.665792, nAl2O3=0.042436, nCaSiO3=0.004596, nNa2SiO3=0.038493,
↪nKAlSiO4=0.062105, \
    nPlagAb=0.8, nPlagAn=0.1, nPlagSn=0.1, nAlkAb=0.3, nAlkAn=0.1, nAlkSn=0.
↪6):
    global m
    nLiq = np.zeros(c)
    nLiq[0] = nSiO2
    nLiq[1] = nAl2O3
    nLiq[2] = nCaSiO3
    nLiq[3] = nNa2SiO3
    nLiq[4] = nKAlSiO4
    m[0] = nLiq[0] # SiO2
    m[1] = 0.0 # TiO2
    m[2] = nLiq[1] # Al2O3
    m[3] = 0.0 # Fe2O3
    m[4] = 0.0 # Cr2O3
    m[5] = 0.0 # Fe2SiO4
    m[6] = 0.0 # Mn2SiO4
    m[7] = 0.0 # Mg2SiO4
    m[8] = 0.0 # NiSi1/2O2
    m[9] = 0.0 # CoSi1/2O2
    m[10] = nLiq[2] # CaSiO3
    m[11] = nLiq[3] # Na2SiO3
    m[12] = nLiq[4] # KAlSiO4
    m[13] = 0.0 # Ca3(PO4)2
    m[14] = 0.0 # H2O
    mPlag[0] = nPlagAb
    mPlag[1] = nPlagAn
    mPlag[2] = nPlagSn
    mAlk[0] = nAlkAb
    mAlk[1] = nAlkAn
    mAlk[2] = nAlkSn
    return nLiq
```

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Choose a temperature and pressure. The thermodynamic properties of quartz are only functions of temperature and pressure

```
t = 755.0 + 273.15 # K
p = 1750.0 # bars
mu0Qz = quartz.gibbs_energy(t, p)
```

Find an initial guess that is consistent with the constraints. Use the scipy optimization function minimize to solve the non-linear system of chemical potential equalities subject to bound constraints

```
def fcon(x):
    global m, mPlag, mAlk
    setMoles(nSiO2=x[0], nAl2O3=x[1], nCaSiO3=x[2], nNa2SiO3=x[3], nKAlSiO4=x[4], \
            nPlagAb=x[5], nPlagAn=x[6], nPlagSn=x[7], nAlkAb=x[8], nAlkAn=x[9], \
            nAlkSn=x[10])
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    result = (mu0Qz-muLiq[0])**2
    omegaAb = 5.0*muLiq[0]/2.0 + muLiq[2]/2.0 + muLiq[11]/2.0
    omegaAn = muLiq[0] + muLiq[2] + muLiq[10]
    omegaSn = 2.0*muLiq[0] + muLiq[12]
    muPlag = plagioclase.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mPlag)[0]
    result += (muPlag[0] - omegaAb)**2
    result += (muPlag[1] - omegaAn)**2
    result += (muPlag[2] - omegaSn)**2
    muAlk = sanidine.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mAlk)[0]
    result += (muAlk[0] - omegaAb)**2
    result += (muAlk[1] - omegaAn)**2
    result += (muAlk[2] - omegaSn)**2
    return result
result = opt.minimize(fcon,np.array([0.665792, 0.042436, 0.004596, 0.038493, 0.062105,
    0.8, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3, 0.1, 0.6]), \
                    bounds=((0, None), (0, None), (0, None), (0, None), (0, None), (0,
    None), \
                            (0, None), (0, None), (0, None), (0, None), (0, None)))
print (result)
nLiqSiO2 = result.x[0]
nLiqAl2O3 = result.x[1]
nLiqCaSiO3 = result.x[2]
nLiqNa2SiO3 = result.x[3]
nLiqKAlSiO4 = result.x[4]
nPlagAb = result.x[5]
nPlagAn = result.x[6]
nPlagSn = result.x[7]
nAlkAb = result.x[8]
nAlkAn = result.x[9]
nAlkSn = result.x[10]
nQz = nPhaseFix
setBulkComposition(nSiO2=nLiqSiO2, nAl2O3=nLiqAl2O3, nCaSiO3=nLiqCaSiO3, \
    nNa2SiO3=nLiqNa2SiO3, \
                    nKAlSiO4=nLiqKAlSiO4, nQz=nQz, nPlagAb=nPlagAb, nPlagAn=nPlagAn, \
    nPlagSn=nPlagSn, \
                    nAlkAb=nAlkAb, nAlkAn=nAlkAn, nAlkSn=nAlkSn)
print ('{0:<10.10s} {1:10.8f} moles'.format('SiO2', bc[0][0]))
print ('{0:<10.10s} {1:10.8f} moles'.format('Al2O3', bc[1][0]))
print ('{0:<10.10s} {1:10.8f} moles'.format('CaO', bc[2][0]))
print ('{0:<10.10s} {1:10.8f} moles'.format('Na2O', bc[3][0]))
print ('{0:<10.10s} {1:10.8f} moles'.format('K2O', bc[4][0]))
```

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```
print ('Residuals:')
muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Qz mu', mu0Qz-muLiq[0]))
omegaAb = 5.0*muLiq[0]/2.0 + muLiq[2]/2.0 + muLiq[11]/2.0
omegaAn = muLiq[0] + muLiq[2] + muLiq[10]
omegaSn = 2.0*muLiq[0] + muLiq[12]
muPlag = plagioclase.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mPlag)[0]
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Plag Ab mu', muPlag[0] - omegaAb))
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Plag An mu', muPlag[1] - omegaAn))
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Plag Sn mu', muPlag[2] - omegaSn))
muAlk = sanidine.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mAlk)[0]
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Alk Ab mu', muAlk[0] - omegaAb))
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Alk An mu', muAlk[1] - omegaAn))
print('{0:<10.10s} {1:13.6e} J'.format('Alk Sn mu', muAlk[2] - omegaSn))
```

```
fun: 0.002292989316135574
hess_inv: <11x11 LbfgsInvHessProduct with dtype=float64>
jac: array([[ 3.03501638e+02,  2.69773675e+01, -1.49739298e+04,  2.
↪73165036e+04,
           -7.26357342e+02,  1.66866005e+02,  1.74664244e+02, -3.98192803e+02,
           -4.32372492e+02,  2.84678196e+02,  5.87046836e+02])
message: 'CONVERGENCE: REL_REDUCTION_OF_F_<=_FACTR*EPSMCH'
nfev: 1560
nit: 80
njev: 130
status: 0
success: True
x: array([2.06251558, 0.48324949, 0.00489534, 0.00256631, 0.259706 ,
          0.77197207, 0.27565213, 0.43758921, 1.01152446, 0.3611878 ,
          0.57338776])
SiO2      12.98678360 moles
Al2O3     2.64717917 moles
CaO       0.64173526 moles
Na2O      0.89431458 moles
K2O       0.63534149 moles
Residuals:
Qz mu     6.463567e-03 J
Plag Ab mu 2.306392e-04 J
Plag An mu -1.184212e-02 J
Plag Sn mu 2.446533e-02 J
Alk Ab mu  8.173905e-03 J
Alk An mu  3.351349e-02 J
Alk Sn mu -1.811833e-02 J
```

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Set up bulk composition constraint matrix - matrix is constant

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_{\text{SiO}_2} \\ b_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} \\ b_{\text{CaO}} \\ b_{\text{Na}_2\text{O}} \\ b_{\text{K}_2\text{O}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 3 & 2 & 3 & 3 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 1 & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \\ n_{\text{Qz}} \\ n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}} \\ n_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}} \\ n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}} \\ n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}} \\ n_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}} \\ n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}} \end{bmatrix}$$

```

C = np.array([[1,0,1,1,1,1,3,2,3,3,2,3],[0,1,0,0,0.5,0,0.5,1,0.5,0.5,1,0.5],[0,0,1,0,
→0,0,0,1,0,0,1,0],\
              [0,0,0,1,0,0,0.5,0,0,0.5,0,0],[0,0,0,0,0.5,0,0,0,0.5,0,0,0.5]])

```

... and project it into the null space of fixed constraints - yields a constant matrix

```

eps = np.finfo(float).eps
CTf = C[:,c:].transpose()
U,S,VT = np.linalg.svd(CTf)
rank = 0
for i in range(0,c):
    if S[i] > 10.0*eps:
        rank +=1
print ('CTf rank: ',rank)
VTff = VT[rank:,:]
Cproj = np.matmul(VTff, C)
for i in range(0,Cproj.shape[0]):
    for j in range(0,Cproj.shape[1]):
        if abs(Cproj[i][j]) < 10.0*eps:
            Cproj[i][j] = 0.0
print ('Cproj:')
print (Cproj)
bcproj = np.matmul(VTff, bc)
print ('bcproj')
print (bcproj)

```

```

CTf rank:  4
Cproj:
[[ 0.  -0.5  0.5  0.5  0.  0.  0.  0.  0.  0.  0.  0. ]]
bcproj
[[-0.23789392]]

```

Define the Khorzhinski potential function

$$\begin{aligned}
 L = & G^{\text{liq}} \left(n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}, n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}, n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}, n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}, n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}} \right) + n_{\text{Qz}} \mu_{\text{Qz}}^0 + G^{\text{plag}} \left(n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}, n_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}, n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}} \right) + G^{\text{alk}} \left(n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}, n_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}, n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}} \right) \\
 & - n_{\text{Qz}} \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}} - \left(n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}} + n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}} \right) \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}} - \left(n_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}} + n_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}} \right) \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}} - \left(n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}} + n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}} \right) \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}
 \end{aligned}$$

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where

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_{Ab}^{liq} &= \frac{5}{2}\mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2}\mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2}\mu_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq} \\ \Omega_{An}^{liq} &= \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} + \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq} + \frac{1}{2}\mu_{CaSiO_3}^{liq} \\ \Omega_{Sn}^{liq} &= 2\mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} + \mu_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}\end{aligned}$$

```
def Khorzhinskii(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
                 nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t=1100.0, \
                 p=1750.0):
    setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
            nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn)
    Gliq = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m)
    Gplag = plagioclase.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mPlag)
    Galk = sanidine.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mAlk)
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)
    omegaAb = 5.0*muLiq[0]/2.0 + muLiq[2]/2.0 + muLiq[11]/2.0
    omegaAn = muLiq[0] + muLiq[2] + muLiq[10]
    omegaSn = 2.0*muLiq[0] + muLiq[12]
    result = Gliq + nQz*(mu0Qz-muLiq[0]) + Gplag + Galk
    result += - (nPlagAb+nAlkAb)*omegaAb - (nPlagAn+nAlkAn)*omegaAn - \
    (nPlagSn+nAlkSn)*omegaSn
    return result
```

Define the gradient of the Khorzhinskii potential

$$\mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_{SiO_2}^{liq}} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_{SiO_2}^{liq}} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_{SiO_2}^{liq}} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_{SiO_2}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{CaSiO_3}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{CaSiO_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq}} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq}} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq}} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq}} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq}} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq}} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq} - n_{Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}}{\partial n_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \frac{\partial \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}} \\ \mu_{Qz}^o - \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Ab}^{plag} - \Omega_{Ab}^{liq} \\ \mu_{An}^{plag} - \Omega_{An}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Sn}^{plag} - \Omega_{Sn}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Ab}^{alk} - \Omega_{Ab}^{liq} \\ \mu_{An}^{alk} - \Omega_{An}^{liq} \\ \mu_{Sn}^{alk} - \Omega_{Sn}^{liq} \end{bmatrix}$$

```
def Gradient(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
            nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t=1100.0, p=1750.0, \
            deriv=0):
    setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
            nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn)
    dgdm = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':1})[0]
    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    omegaAb = 5.0*muLiq[0]/2.0 + muLiq[2]/2.0 + muLiq[11]/2.0
    omegaAn = muLiq[0] + muLiq[2] + muLiq[10]
    omegaSn = 2.0*muLiq[0] + muLiq[12]
    d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
```

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```

OmegaAb = lambda i: 5.0*d2gdm2[0, i]/2.0 + d2gdm2[2, i]/2.0 + d2gdm2[11, i]/2.0
OmegaAn = lambda i: d2gdm2[0, i] + d2gdm2[2, i] + d2gdm2[10, i]
OmegaSn = lambda i: 2.0*d2gdm2[0, i] + d2gdm2[12, i]

muPlag = plagioclase.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mPlag)[0]
muAlk = sanidine.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mAlk)[0]

result = np.zeros((c+f,1))
result[0] = dgdm[0] - nQz*d2gdm2[0, 0] \
            - (nPlagAb+nAlkAb)*OmegaAb(0) \
            - (nPlagAn+nAlkAn)*OmegaAn(0) \
            - (nPlagSn+nAlkSn)*OmegaSn(0)
result[1] = dgdm[2] - nQz*d2gdm2[0, 2] \
            - (nPlagAb+nAlkAb)*OmegaAb(2) \
            - (nPlagAn+nAlkAn)*OmegaAn(2) \
            - (nPlagSn+nAlkSn)*OmegaSn(2)
result[2] = dgdm[10] - nQz*d2gdm2[0, 10] \
            - (nPlagAb+nAlkAb)*OmegaAb(10) \
            - (nPlagAn+nAlkAn)*OmegaAn(10) \
            - (nPlagSn+nAlkSn)*OmegaSn(10)
result[3] = dgdm[11] - nQz*d2gdm2[0, 11] \
            - (nPlagAb+nAlkAb)*OmegaAb(11) \
            - (nPlagAn+nAlkAn)*OmegaAn(11) \
            - (nPlagSn+nAlkSn)*OmegaSn(11)
result[4] = dgdm[12] - nQz*d2gdm2[0, 12] \
            - (nPlagAb+nAlkAb)*OmegaAb(12) \
            - (nPlagAn+nAlkAn)*OmegaAn(12) \
            - (nPlagSn+nAlkSn)*OmegaSn(12)

result[5] = mu0Qz - dgdm[0]
result[6] = muPlag[0] - omegaAb
result[7] = muPlag[1] - omegaAn
result[8] = muPlag[2] - omegaSn
result[9] = muAlk[0] - omegaAb
result[10] = muAlk[1] - omegaAn
result[11] = muAlk[2] - omegaSn
return result

```

Define a function to compute the “A” constraint matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix}
 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{plag}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{An}}^{\text{plag}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}}}{\partial n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{plag}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}}} \\
 -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{An}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}}} \\
 -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{SiO}_2}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{CaSiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3}^{\text{liq}}} & -\frac{\partial \Omega_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{liq}}}{\partial n_{\text{KAlSiO}_4}^{\text{liq}}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{Ab}}^{\text{alk}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{An}}^{\text{alk}}} & \frac{\partial \mu_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}}}{\partial n_{\text{Sn}}^{\text{alk}}} \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0
 \end{bmatrix}$$

```

def Amatrix(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
            nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t=1100.0, p=1750.
            ->0):

```

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```
setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
        nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn)
d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
d2gdm2Plag = plagioclase.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mPlag, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
d2gdm2Alk = sanidine.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mAlk, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]

OmegaAb = lambda i: 5.0*d2gdm2[0, i]/2.0 + d2gdm2[2, i]/2.0 + d2gdm2[11, i]/2.0
OmegaAn = lambda i: d2gdm2[0, i] + d2gdm2[2, i] + d2gdm2[10, i]
OmegaSn = lambda i: 2.0*d2gdm2[0, i] + d2gdm2[12, i]

bottom = np.zeros((f,c+f))
bottom[0][0] = -d2gdm2[0, 0]
bottom[0][1] = -d2gdm2[0, 2]
bottom[0][2] = -d2gdm2[0, 10]
bottom[0][3] = -d2gdm2[0, 11]
bottom[0][4] = -d2gdm2[0, 12]

bottom[1][0] = -OmegaAb(0)
bottom[1][1] = -OmegaAb(2)
bottom[1][2] = -OmegaAb(10)
bottom[1][3] = -OmegaAb(11)
bottom[1][4] = -OmegaAb(12)
bottom[1][6] = d2gdm2Plag[0, 0]
bottom[1][7] = d2gdm2Plag[0, 1]
bottom[1][8] = d2gdm2Plag[0, 2]

bottom[2][0] = -OmegaAn(0)
bottom[2][1] = -OmegaAn(2)
bottom[2][2] = -OmegaAn(10)
bottom[2][3] = -OmegaAn(11)
bottom[2][4] = -OmegaAn(12)
bottom[2][6] = d2gdm2Plag[1, 0]
bottom[2][7] = d2gdm2Plag[1, 1]
bottom[2][8] = d2gdm2Plag[1, 2]

bottom[3][0] = -OmegaSn(0)
bottom[3][1] = -OmegaSn(2)
bottom[3][2] = -OmegaSn(10)
bottom[3][3] = -OmegaSn(11)
bottom[3][4] = -OmegaSn(12)
bottom[3][6] = d2gdm2Plag[2, 0]
bottom[3][7] = d2gdm2Plag[2, 1]
bottom[3][8] = d2gdm2Plag[2, 2]

bottom[4][0] = -OmegaAb(0)
bottom[4][1] = -OmegaAb(2)
bottom[4][2] = -OmegaAb(10)
bottom[4][3] = -OmegaAb(11)
bottom[4][4] = -OmegaAb(12)
bottom[4][9] = d2gdm2Alk[0, 0]
bottom[4][10] = d2gdm2Alk[0, 1]
bottom[4][11] = d2gdm2Alk[0, 2]

bottom[5][0] = -OmegaAn(0)
bottom[5][1] = -OmegaAn(2)
bottom[5][2] = -OmegaAn(10)
```

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Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

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```

bottom[5][3] = -Domegan(11)
bottom[5][4] = -Domegan(12)
bottom[5][9] = d2gdm2Alk[1, 0]
bottom[5][10] = d2gdm2Alk[1, 1]
bottom[5][11] = d2gdm2Alk[1, 2]

bottom[6][5] = 1.0

result = np.vstack((Cproj, bottom))
return result

```

Define the Lagrangian of the Khorzhinskii function

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Lambda = & G^{liq} (n_{SiO_2}^{liq}, n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}, n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq}, n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq}, n_{KAlSiO_4}^{liq}) + n_{Qz} \mu_{Qz}^o + G^{plag} (n_{Ab}^{plag}, n_{An}^{plag}, n_{Sn}^{plag}) + G^{alk} (n_{Ab}^{alk}, n_{An}^{alk}, n_{Sn}^{alk}) \\
 & - n_{Qz} \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \Omega_{Ab}^{liq} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \Omega_{An}^{liq} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \Omega_{Sn}^{liq} \\
 - \lambda_b \left[\frac{1}{2} (n_{CaSiO_3}^{liq} + n_{Na_2SiO_3}^{liq} - n_{Al_2O_3}^{liq}) - \frac{1}{2} (b_{CaO} + b_{Na_2O} + b_{K_2O} - b_{Al_2O_3}) \right] & - \lambda_{Qz} (\mu_{SiO_2}^{qtz} - \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}) - \lambda_{Ab}^{plag} (\mu_{Ab}^{plag} - \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}) \\
 - \lambda_{An}^{plag} (\mu_{An}^{plag} - \Omega_{An}^{liq}) - \lambda_{Sn}^{plag} (\mu_{Sn}^{plag} - \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}) - \lambda_{Ab}^{alk} (\mu_{Ab}^{alk} - \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}) - \lambda_{An}^{alk} (\mu_{An}^{alk} - \Omega_{An}^{liq}) - \lambda_{n_{Qz}} (n_{Qz} - n_{Fix}) &
 \end{aligned}$$

```

def Lagrangian(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
               nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t=1100.0, \
               p=1750.0):
    nLiq = setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
                  nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn)

    result = Khorzhinskii(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
                          nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t, \
                          p)

    muLiq = liquid.chem_potential(t, p, mol=m)[0]
    omegaAb = 5.0*muLiq[0]/2.0 + muLiq[2]/2.0 + muLiq[11]/2.0
    omegaAn = muLiq[0] + muLiq[2] + muLiq[10]
    omegaSn = 2.0*muLiq[0] + muLiq[12]

    muPlag = plagioclase.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mPlag)[0]
    muAlk = sanidine.chem_potential(t, p, mol=mAlk)[0]

    nFix = np.zeros((f,1))
    n = np.vstack((nLiq,nFix))
    # now add the Lagrange terms
    temp = np.matmul(Cproj, n)
    temp = np.subtract(temp, bcproj)
    result -= (np.dot(temp.transpose(), xLambda[0])[0][0])
    result -= xLambda[1][0]*(muQz-muLiq[0])
    result -= xLambda[2][0]*(muPlag[0]-omegaAb)
    result -= xLambda[3][0]*(muPlag[1]-omegaAn)
    result -= xLambda[4][0]*(muPlag[2]-omegaSn)
    result -= xLambda[5][0]*(muAlk[0]-omegaAb)
    result -= xLambda[6][0]*(muAlk[1]-omegaAn)
    result -= xLambda[7][0]*(nQz-nPhaseFix)
    return result

```

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Define the Wronskian of the Lagrangian function. Elements of the Wronskian are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \Lambda}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} = & \frac{\partial^2 G^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} + \frac{\partial^2 G^{plag}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} + \frac{\partial^2 G^{alk}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \delta_{i,Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - \delta_{j,Qz} \frac{\partial \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - (n_{Qz} - \lambda_{Qz}) \frac{\partial^2 \mu_{SiO_2}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \\ & - (\delta_{i,plag-Ab} + \delta_{i,alk-Ab}) \frac{\Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - (\delta_{j,plag-Ab} + \delta_{j,alk-Ab}) \frac{\Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - (n_{Ab}^{plag} + n_{Ab}^{alk}) \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \\ & - (\delta_{i,plag-An} + \delta_{i,alk-An}) \frac{\Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - (\delta_{j,plag-An} + \delta_{j,alk-An}) \frac{\Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - (n_{An}^{plag} + n_{An}^{alk}) \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \\ & - (\delta_{i,plag-Sn} + \delta_{i,alk-Sn}) \frac{\Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_j} - (\delta_{j,plag-Sn} + \delta_{j,alk-Sn}) \frac{\Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i} - (n_{Sn}^{plag} + n_{Sn}^{alk}) \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \\ & - \lambda_{Ab}^{plag} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu_{Ab}^{plag}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \right) - \lambda_{An}^{plag} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu_{An}^{plag}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \right) - \lambda_{Sn}^{plag} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu_{Sn}^{plag}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Sn}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \right) \\ & - \lambda_{Ab}^{alk} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu_{Ab}^{alk}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{Ab}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \right) - \lambda_{An}^{alk} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu_{An}^{alk}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} - \frac{\partial^2 \Omega_{An}^{liq}}{\partial n_i \partial n_j} \right) \end{aligned}$$

```
def Wronskian(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
             nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t=1100.0, \
             p=1750.0):
    nLiq = setMoles(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
                  nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn)
    w = np.zeros((c+f, c+f))
    ind = [0, 2, 10, 11, 12]

    d2gdm2 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    for i in range(0, 5):
        for j in range(i, 5):
            w[i][j] += d2gdm2[ind[i], ind[j]]
            w[j][i] = w[i][j]
    d2gdm2Plag = plagioclase.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mPlag, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    for i in range(0, 3):
        for j in range(i, 3):
            w[i+6][j+6] += d2gdm2Plag[i, j]
            w[j+6][i+6] = w[i+6][j+6]
    d2gdm2Alk = sanidine.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mAlk, deriv={'dmol':2})[0]
    for i in range(0, 3):
        for j in range(i, 3):
            w[i+9][j+9] += d2gdm2Alk[i, j]
            w[j+9][i+9] = w[i+9][j+9]

    for i in range(0, 5):
        w[5][i] -= d2gdm2[0, ind[i]]
        w[i][5] = w[5][i]

    OmegaAb = lambda i: 5.0*d2gdm2[0, i]/2.0 + d2gdm2[2, i]/2.0 + d2gdm2[11, i]/2.0
    OmegaAn = lambda i: d2gdm2[0, i] + d2gdm2[2, i] + d2gdm2[10, i]
    OmegaSn = lambda i: 2.0*d2gdm2[0, i] + d2gdm2[12, i]

    for i in range(0, 5):
        w[6][i] += -OmegaAb(ind[i])
        w[i][6] = w[6][i]
        w[9][i] += -OmegaAb(ind[i])
        w[i][9] = w[9][i]
        w[7][i] += -OmegaAn(ind[i])
        w[i][7] = w[7][i]
        w[10][i] += -OmegaAn(ind[i])
        w[i][10] = w[10][i]
        w[8][i] += -OmegaSn(ind[i])
        w[i][8] = w[8][i]
        w[11][i] += -OmegaSn(ind[i])
        w[i][11] = w[11][i]
```

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```

d3gdm3 = liquid.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=m, deriv={'dmol':3})[0]
D2omegaAb = lambda i, j : 5.0*d3gdm3[0, i, j]/2.0 + d3gdm3[2, i, j]/2.0 +
↳d3gdm3[11, i, j]/2.0
D2omegaAn = lambda i, j : d3gdm3[0, i, j] + d3gdm3[2, i, j] + d3gdm3[10, i, j]
D2omegaSn = lambda i, j : 2.0*d3gdm3[0, i, j] + d3gdm3[12, i, j]
d3gdm3Plag = plagioclase.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mPlag, deriv={'dmol':3})[0]
d3gdm3Alk = sanidine.gibbs_energy(t, p, mol=mAlk, deriv={'dmol':3})[0]

for i in range(0,5):
    for j in range(i,5):
        w[i][j] -= (nQz-xLambda[1][0])*d3gdm3[0, ind[i], ind[j]]
        w[i][j] -= (nPlagAb+nAlkAb-xLambda[2][0]-xLambda[5][0])*D2omegaAb(ind[i],
↳ind[j])
        w[i][j] -= (nPlagAn+nAlkAn-xLambda[3][0]-xLambda[6][0])*D2omegaAn(ind[i],
↳ind[j])
        w[i][j] -= (nPlagSn+nAlkSn-xLambda[4][0])*D2omegaSn(ind[i],ind[j])
        w[j][i] = w[i][j]

for i in range(0,3):
    for j in range(i,3):
        w[i+6][j+6] -= xLambda[2][0]*d3gdm3Plag[0, i, j]
        w[i+6][j+6] -= xLambda[3][0]*d3gdm3Plag[1, i, j]
        w[i+6][j+6] -= xLambda[4][0]*d3gdm3Plag[2, i, j]
        w[j+6][i+6] = w[i+6][j+6]
        w[i+9][j+9] -= xLambda[5][0]*d3gdm3Alk[0, i, j]
        w[i+9][j+9] -= xLambda[6][0]*d3gdm3Alk[1, i, j]
        w[j+9][i+9] = w[i+9][j+9]

return w

```

Form the QR decomposition of A. Note that A must be square, so zero filled rows are added

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{QR} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_1 & \mathbf{Q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_1 \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$$

and \mathbf{Q}_2^T is the matrix \mathbf{Z}

```

A = Amatrix(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
            nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t, p)
fmt = '{:9.1e}'*12
print ("A matrix:", A.shape)
for i in range(0, A.shape[0]):
    print (fmt.format(A[i][0], A[i][1], A[i][2], A[i][3], A[i][4], A[i][5], A[i][6],
↳A[i][7], A[i][8], \
                    A[i][9], A[i][10], A[i][11]))

# use
bottom = np.zeros((4,c+f))
A = np.vstack((A, bottom))
Q,R = lin.qr(A,mode='full')
# or
#R,Q = lin.rq(A,mode='full')
print ("Q matrix:", Q.shape)
for i in range(0,Q.shape[0]):
    print (fmt.format(Q[i][0], Q[i][1], Q[i][2], Q[i][3], Q[i][4], Q[i][5], Q[i][6],
↳Q[i][7], Q[i][8], \

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```

        Q[i][9], Q[i][10], Q[i][11]))
print ("R matrix:", R.shape)
for i in range(0,R.shape[0]):
    print (fmt.format(R[i][0], R[i][1], R[i][2], R[i][3], R[i][4], R[i][5], R[i][6], \
↪R[i][7], R[i][8], \
        R[i][9], R[i][10], R[i][11]))
Z = Q[f+1:,:].transpose()
print ("Z matrix", Z.shape)
fmt = '{:9.1e}'*4
for i in range(0,Z.shape[0]):
    print (fmt.format(Z[i][0], Z[i][1], Z[i][2], Z[i][3]))

```

```

A matrix: (8, 12)
  0.0e+00 -5.0e-01  5.0e-01  5.0e-01  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-2.7e+03  7.8e+03  2.1e+03  6.6e+03  6.7e+03  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
 5.1e+02  8.9e+03  8.9e+02 -1.7e+06 -4.2e+03  0.0e+00  4.8e+03 -1.1e+04 -1.8e+03  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
 7.2e+03 -8.8e+03 -1.7e+06 -6.6e+03 -8.3e+03  0.0e+00 -1.1e+04  1.4e+04  1.0e+04  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
 1.3e+03  1.2e+04 -6.9e+03 -2.5e+04 -3.2e+04  0.0e+00 -1.8e+03  1.0e+04 -3.2e+03  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
 5.1e+02  8.9e+03  8.9e+02 -1.7e+06 -4.2e+03  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪3.7e+03 -8.1e+03 -1.4e+03
 7.2e+03 -8.8e+03 -1.7e+06 -6.6e+03 -8.3e+03  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪8.1e+03  1.0e+04  7.8e+03
 0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  1.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
Q matrix: (12, 12)
  0.0e+00  2.6e-05 -7.1e-06 -2.4e-05  1.0e+00  0.0e+00 -1.6e-12  1.1e-12  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
 2.5e-01 -2.5e-01  9.3e-01  1.3e-01  1.6e-05  0.0e+00 -9.5e-17  2.8e-16  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-4.8e-02 -4.9e-01 -4.7e-02 -5.1e-01 -5.4e-08  0.0e+00 -2.9e-01  6.4e-01  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-6.8e-01  4.9e-02  2.0e-01 -1.6e-03  9.0e-08  0.0e+00  6.4e-01  2.9e-01  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-1.2e-01 -6.8e-01 -2.5e-01  6.8e-01  3.2e-05  0.0e+00 -3.9e-17  7.1e-17  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-4.8e-02 -4.9e-01 -4.7e-02 -5.1e-01 -5.4e-08  0.0e+00  2.9e-01 -6.4e-01  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-6.8e-01  4.9e-02  2.0e-01 -1.6e-03  9.0e-08 -0.0e+00 -6.4e-01 -2.9e-01  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -1.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  1.0e+00  0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  ↪
↪1.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00  1.0e+00  0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  ↪
↪0.0e+00 -0.0e+00  1.0e+00
R matrix: (12, 12)

```

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```

-1.1e+04  1.2e+04  2.3e+06  1.7e+05  1.7e+04  0.0e+00  7.2e+03 -1.0e+04 -6.4e+03  -
↵5.3e+03 -6.7e+03 -5.2e+03
  0.0e+00 -1.9e+04 -1.7e+05  1.6e+06  2.3e+04  0.0e+00 -1.6e+03 -1.0e+03  3.6e+03  -
↵2.2e+03  4.5e+03  1.1e+03
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -6.8e+05  1.7e+05  1.1e+04  0.0e+00 -1.9e+03  7.0e+02  2.9e+03  -
↵1.8e+03  2.4e+03  1.6e+03
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  1.7e+06 -1.7e+04  0.0e+00 -3.7e+03  1.2e+04 -1.3e+03  -
↵1.9e+03  4.1e+03  7.0e+02
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -9.2e-01  0.0e+00 -6.0e-02  3.3e-01 -1.0e-01  -
↵9.3e-04  1.4e-03  7.8e-04
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -1.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  -
↵0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -8.3e+03  1.2e+04  7.1e+03  -
↵6.3e+03 -9.1e+03 -5.4e+03
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00 -2.9e+03  1.8e+03  -
↵2.3e-02  2.2e+03 -1.4e+03
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  -
↵0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  -
↵0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  -
↵0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  -
↵0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  -
↵0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
Z matrix (12, 4)
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00
-0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00
  1.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  1.0e+00 -0.0e+00 -0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  1.0e+00 -0.0e+00
  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  0.0e+00  1.0e+00

```

Form the vector of Lagrange multipliers

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{A}^T \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{n_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{n_{c-f}} \\ \lambda_{\phi_1} \\ \vdots \\ \lambda_{\phi_f} \end{bmatrix}$$

```

print ("Gradient:")
g = Gradient(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
            nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t, p)
for i in range(0,g.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(g[i][0]))
print ("Lambda:")
xLambda = np.linalg.lstsq(A.transpose(),g, rcond=None)[0]
for i in range(0,xLambda.shape[0]):
    print ("{0:10.3e}".format(xLambda[i][0]))

```

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

```

Gradient:
-9.777e+05
-1.739e+06
-2.907e+06
-4.882e+06
-2.385e+06
 6.464e-03
 2.306e-04
-1.184e-02
 2.447e-02
 8.188e-03
 3.344e-02
-1.809e-02
Lambda:
 1.050e+07
 2.651e+02
 1.384e+02
 5.039e+01
 1.224e+02
-1.331e+02
-4.584e+01
 6.464e-03
 0.000e+00
 0.000e+00
 0.000e+00
 0.000e+00

```

Compute the Wronskian of the Lagrangian

```

W = Wronskian(nLiqSiO2, nLiqAl2O3, nLiqCaSiO3, nLiqNa2SiO3, nLiqKAlSiO4, \
             nQz, nPlagAb, nPlagAn, nPlagSn, nAlkAb, nAlkAn, nAlkSn, t, p)
fmt = '{:9.1e}'*12
for i in range(0,W.shape[0]):
    print (fmt.format(W[i][0], W[i][1], W[i][2], W[i][3], W[i][4], W[i][5], W[i][6],
↵W[i][7], W[i][8],
                        W[i][9], W[i][10], W[i][11]))

```

```

 2.7e+03 -7.8e+03 -2.1e+03 -6.6e+03 -6.7e+03 -2.7e+03 5.1e+02 7.2e+03 1.3e+03 ↵
↵5.1e+02 7.2e+03 1.3e+03
-7.8e+03 3.1e+04 -1.5e+04 -1.0e+04 3.8e+03 7.8e+03 8.9e+03 -8.8e+03 1.2e+04 ↵
↵8.9e+03 -8.8e+03 1.2e+04
-2.1e+03 -1.5e+04 1.7e+06 2.4e+04 1.1e+04 2.1e+03 8.9e+02 -1.7e+06 -6.9e+03 ↵
↵8.9e+02 -1.7e+06 -6.9e+03
-6.6e+03 -1.0e+04 2.4e+04 3.4e+06 3.8e+04 6.6e+03 -1.7e+06 -6.6e+03 -2.5e+04 ↵
↵1.7e+06 -6.6e+03 -2.5e+04
-6.7e+03 3.8e+03 1.1e+04 3.8e+04 4.5e+04 6.7e+03 -4.2e+03 -8.3e+03 -3.2e+04 ↵
↵4.2e+03 -8.3e+03 -3.2e+04
-2.7e+03 7.8e+03 2.1e+03 6.6e+03 6.7e+03 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 ↵
↵0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00
 5.1e+02 8.9e+03 8.9e+02 -1.7e+06 -4.2e+03 0.0e+00 4.1e+05 -1.3e+06 2.7e+05 ↵
↵0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00
 7.2e+03 -8.8e+03 -1.7e+06 -6.6e+03 -8.3e+03 0.0e+00 -1.3e+06 5.3e+04 -1.7e+05 ↵
↵0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00
 1.3e+03 1.2e+04 -6.9e+03 -2.5e+04 -3.2e+04 0.0e+00 2.7e+05 -1.7e+05 -5.9e+05 ↵
↵0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00
 5.1e+02 8.9e+03 8.9e+02 -1.7e+06 -4.2e+03 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 ↵
↵5.2e+04 -6.9e+05 -1.9e+05

```

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Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

(continued from previous page)

```

7.2e+03 -8.8e+03 -1.7e+06 -6.6e+03 -8.3e+03 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 -
↪6.9e+05 -7.4e+05 9.3e+03
1.3e+03 1.2e+04 -6.9e+03 -2.5e+04 -3.2e+04 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 0.0e+00 -
↪1.9e+05 9.3e+03 1.1e+05

```

Next project the gradient and the Wronskian. The search direction ($\Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$) is given by

$$\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{Z} \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i = -\mathbf{Z}^T \mathbf{g}$$

and $\mathbf{n}_\phi^{i+1} = \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i$ gives the quadratic approximation to the minimum, which must be adjusted to maintain the non-linear equality constraints

$$\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\phi^{i+1} = s \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \mathbf{n}_\phi^i + \Delta \mathbf{n}_\phi^{corr}$$

```

ZTg = np.matmul(Z.transpose(), g)
ZTWZ = np.matmul(Z.transpose(), np.matmul(W, Z))
print("Z^T g", ZTg.shape)
for i in range(0, ZTg.shape[0]):
    print("{0:10.3e}".format(ZTg[i][0]))
print("Z^T W Z", ZTWZ.shape)
for i in range(0, ZTWZ.shape[0]):
    print("{0:10.3e} {1:10.3e} {2:10.3e} {3:10.3e}".format(ZTWZ[i][0], ZTWZ[i][1], ↪
↪ZTWZ[i][2], ZTWZ[i][3]))

```

```

Z^T g (4, 1)
2.447e-02
8.188e-03
3.344e-02
-1.809e-02
Z^T W Z (4, 4)
-5.904e+05 0.000e+00 0.000e+00 0.000e+00
0.000e+00 -5.204e+04 6.853e+05 -1.913e+05
0.000e+00 6.853e+05 -7.384e+05 9.272e+03
0.000e+00 -1.913e+05 9.272e+03 1.063e+05

```

... and solve for the correction vector

```

x = lin.solve(ZTWZ, ZTg)
print("Solution in the null space:")
for i in range(0, x.shape[0]):
    print("{0:10.3e}".format(x[i][0]))
deltan = np.matmul(Z, x)
print("Inflated Solution:")
for i in range(0, deltan.shape[0]):
    print("{0:10.3e}".format(deltan[i][0]))

```

```

Solution in the null space:
-4.144e-08
3.282e-08
-1.620e-08
-1.098e-07
Inflated Solution:
0.000e+00

```

(continues on next page)

Calculating Equilibrium Phase Assemblages in Systems Subject to Generalized Constraints on System Chemical Potentials

(continued from previous page)

```
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
0.000e+00
-4.144e-08
3.282e-08
-1.620e-08
-1.098e-07
```

Final solution

```
print ("n SiO2    liq = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nLiqSiO2, nLiqSiO2+deltan[0][0]))
print ("n Al2O3    liq = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nLiqAl2O3,
↳nLiqAl2O3+deltan[1][0]))
print ("n CaSiO3    liq = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nLiqCaSiO3,
↳nLiqCaSiO3+deltan[2][0]))
print ("n Na2SiO3    liq = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nLiqNa2SiO3,
↳nLiqNa2SiO3+deltan[3][0]))
print ("n KAlSiO4    liq = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nLiqKAlSiO4,
↳nLiqKAlSiO4+deltan[4][0]))
print ("n Qz      = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nQz, nQz+deltan[5][0]))
print ("n Plag Ab   = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nPlagAb, nPlagAb+deltan[6][0]))
print ("n Plag An   = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nPlagAn, nPlagAn+deltan[7][0]))
print ("n Plag Sn   = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nPlagSn, nPlagSn+deltan[8][0]))
print ("n Alk Ab    = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nAlkAb, nAlkAb+deltan[9][0]))
print ("n Alk An    = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nAlkAn, nAlkAn+deltan[10][0]))
print ("n Alk Sn    = {0:8.6f} -> {1:8.6f}".format(nAlkSn, nAlkSn+deltan[11][0]))
```

```
n SiO2    liq = 2.062516 -> 2.062516
n Al2O3    liq = 0.483249 -> 0.483249
n CaSiO3    liq = 0.004895 -> 0.004895
n Na2SiO3    liq = 0.002566 -> 0.002566
n KAlSiO4    liq = 0.259706 -> 0.259706
n Qz      = 1.000000 -> 1.000000
n Plag Ab   = 0.771972 -> 0.771972
n Plag An   = 0.275652 -> 0.275652
n Plag Sn   = 0.437589 -> 0.437589
n Alk Ab    = 1.011524 -> 1.011524
n Alk An    = 0.361188 -> 0.361188
n Alk Sn    = 0.573388 -> 0.573388
```

Part IV

References Cited

REFERENCES CITED

Part V

Appendix

EXTRA MATERIAL TO DESCRIBE DERIVATIVES

Khorzhinskii potential:

$$L = G(\mathbf{n}, T, P) - (\mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{n}) \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} - \left(\mathbf{r}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{n}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} + \mathbf{n} \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}^T}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \right) \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P) - (\mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{n}) \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}}$$

note

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{n}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{I}, \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}^T}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{r}$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} - \mathbf{r} \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P) - (\mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{n}) \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 L}{\partial \mathbf{n}^2} = \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}^2} - \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \mathbf{r}^T - \mathbf{r} \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} - (\mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{n}) \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}^2}$$

The Lagrangian:

$$\Lambda = L - \lambda (\Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P) - \Phi^{fix}(T, P))$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Lambda}{\partial \mathbf{n}^2} = -\lambda \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}^2}$$

Constraint derivatives:

$$\Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P) = \mathbf{r}^T \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \frac{\partial^2 G(\mathbf{n}, T, P)}{\partial \mathbf{n}^2} \mathbf{r}$$

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Herbert B. Callen. *Thermodynamics and an Introduction to Thermostatistics, 2nd ed.* John Wiley and Sons, 1985.
- [2] P. Duhem. *Traité élémentaire de Mécanique chimique, fondée sur la Thermodynamique.* Volume 4. Paris: Librairie scientifique, A. Hermann, 1899.
- [3] Mark S Ghiorso and Peter B Kelemen. Evaluating reaction stoichiometry in magmatic systems evolving under generalized thermodynamic constraints: examples comparing isothermal and isenthalpic assimilation. *Magmatic Processes: Physicochemical Principles*, 1:319–336, 1987.
- [4] Mark S. Ghiorso. A globally convergent saturation state algorithm applicable to thermodynamic systems with a stable or metastable omni-component phase. *Geochimica Et Cosmochimica Acta*, 103:295-300, FEB 15 2013. doi:{10.1016/j.gca.2012.11.013}.
- [5] MS Ghiorso. Chemical Mass-transfer In Magmatic Processes .1. Thermodynamic Relations And Numerical Algorithms. *Contributions To Mineralogy And Petrology*, 90(2-3):107-120, 1985. doi:{10.1007/BF00378254}.
- [6] J. Willard Gibbs. On the Equilibrium of Heterogeneous Substances. *Transactions of the Connecticut Academy of Arts and Sciences*, 3:108-248, 1876.
- [7] J. Willard Gibbs. On the Equilibrium of Heterogeneous Substances. *Transactions of the Connecticut Academy of Arts and Sciences*, 3:343-524, 1878.
- [8] Dmitriï Sergeevich Korzhinskiï. *Physicochemical Basis of the Analysis of the Paragenesis of Minerals.* Consultants Bureau, 1959.
- [9] Charles L Lawson and Richard J Hanson. *Solving least squares problems.* Prentice-Hall, 1974.
- [10] Ilya Prigogine and Raymond Defay. *Chemical Thermodynamics.* Longmans, Green, 1954.